

Towards Refinable Choreographies

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Abstract

We investigate refinement in the context of choreographies. We introduce refinable global choreographies allowing for the underspecification of protocols, whose interactions can be refined into actual protocols. Arbitrary refinements may spoil *well-formedness*, which are sufficient conditions that guarantee a protocol to be implementable. We introduce a typing discipline that enforces well-formedness of typed choreographies. Then we unveil the relation among refinable choreographies and their admissible refinements in terms of an axiom scheme.

Keywords: Choreography, Refinement, Typing

1. Introduction

2 The advent of structured programming [2] is probably behind the widespread
3 use of refinement methods in computer science. Refinement is paramount in
4 many formal methods, in software engineering, and in verification, because the
5 possibility of structuring a system into simpler components is crucial to tackle
6 the complexity of a system.

7 This paper investigates the refinement of choreographies of message-passing
8 systems. In this domain, a choreography specifies the coordination of distributed
9 components (a.k.a. *participants* or *roles*) by disciplining the exchange of mes-
10 sages. According to W3C [3], a choreography is a contract consisting of a *global*
11 *view* that can be used as a blueprint for defining each participant. A global view
12 is basically an *application-level* protocol realised through the coordination of the
13 corresponding *local views*, the specifications of participants. This description is

*This is a revised and extended version of the conference paper [1].

14 the ground for the so-called top-down engineering of choreographies which can
 be represented with the following diagram:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{Global view} & \xrightarrow{\text{project}} & \text{Local view} \\ & & \xleftarrow{\text{comply}} \\ & & \text{Local systems} \end{array} \quad (1)$$

16 where the ‘projection’ operation produces local views from the global ones and
 the operation ‘comply’ verifies that the behaviour of each participant adheres
 18 to the one of the corresponding local view.

Choreographic approaches are appealing because, unlike orchestration, they
 20 do not require an explicit coordinator (see [4] for a deeper discussion). More-
 over, the global view of a system can be used as a blueprint for the development
 22 of each component. In fact, the projection operation allows to derive local
 views which, as advocated in [3], can be used to independently develop each
 24 component.

Despite the main advantages discussed above, choreographic approaches suf-
 26 fer a main drawback: the lack of support for modular development. This short-
 coming is present in standards such as BPMN or in workflow patterns and
 28 languages [5] and it has been more recently flagged also for choreographic pro-
 gramming [6].

30 We propose a choreographic model of message-passing applications based on
 point-to-point asynchronous communication equipped with a simple refinement
 32 mechanism. Let us illustrate this through some simple examples. This gives us
 the opportunity to informally use *global choreographies* [7, 8] (g-choreographies,
 34 for short), the formalisation of global views adopted here for the technical de-
 velopment of the paper.

36 Consider the g-choreography

$$C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S + C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S; S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C \quad (2)$$

where a client C either sends some meta-data md or a request req to a server
 38 S . The protocol terminates in the former case while, in the latter case, the
 server is supposed to send back a response done to C . The dashed arrows above
 40 represent *refinable interactions*, that is interactions that can be replaced so to
 refine the application-level protocol. For instance, to allow S to send C some
 42 statistical information in the second branch of (2) we can refine $S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C$ with
 $S \xrightarrow{\text{stats}} C; S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C$ and obtain

$$C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S + C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S; S \xrightarrow{\text{stats}} C; S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C \quad (3)$$

44 where the interactions with the solid arrow are now “ground”, namely they
 cannot be further refined.

46 This is our simple refinement mechanism: replace a refinable interaction with
 a more complex (possibly refinable) protocol. A key goal here is to provide a
 48 mechanism of refinement without spoiling *well-formedness* conditions. Basically,
 well-formedness conditions ensure that the application-level protocol modelled

50 by the global view is faithfully executed by the participants that comply with
the projected local views. Let us again explain this with an example. Suppose
52 we refine (2) by replacing each refinable interaction with its ground version
but for $C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S$, which we replace with $C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} B; B \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S$, where B is a brokerage
54 service mediating the exchange of md . We obtain

$$C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} B; B \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S + C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S; S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C \quad (4)$$

The g-choreography above is not well-formed because the broker B is oblivious
56 of the second branch. Namely, B will be stuck waiting for message md should
 C opt for the second branch of the choice.

58 *Contributions & Structure.* This paper proposes a simple approach tailored to
the refinement of global views of choreographies. Firstly, we equip an existing
60 formal language expressing *global choreographies* (g-choreographies, for short)
with a semantics based on event structures (surveyed in Section 2) and identify
62 a typing discipline that checks sufficient conditions for well-formedness (Sec-
tion 3). Secondly, we extend g-choreographies with our refinement mechanism
64 (Section 4). The design choice of our framework is to base refinements on the
concept of *refinable interactions*. Inspired by the action refinement mechanism
66 of process algebra, we consider refinable g-choreographies those where refinable
interactions may occur. Refinable g-choreographies play the role of incomplete
68 specifications where, by repeated replacements of refinable interactions, one can
incrementally attain a fully specified global view.

70 One problem with this process is that refinements may occasionally spoil
well-formedness and hence compromise realisability of global views. To avoid
72 this, we extend the typing discipline of non-refinable or *ground* g-choreographies
to refinable ones, and show that the replacement of a refinable interaction with
74 a g-choreography typable with the same type ensures well-formedness. More-
over, we provide a more fine-grained typing rule for refinable interactions (when
76 compared against [1]), which ensures not only safe replacement, but also that
well typed refinable choreographies can be actually refined into ground ones that
78 have the same type (Section 6). Based on the results in the previous section,
we introduce an axiom scheme for typing refinable interactions in (Section 7),
80 and illustrate its use in the interactive process of refinement via an example.
We discuss related work and draw some conclusions in Section 8.

82 This paper revises and extends [1]. In presenting the results appeared in [1]
we strove for an improved presentation. Section 6 is entirely new.

84 2. Background

We recall basic notions of *event structures* used in Section 3 to give semantics
86 to refinable choreographies. Event structures model concurrency in terms of
partial orders of labelled events. We focus our attention on event structures of
88 communication events. Let \mathcal{P} be a set of *participants* (ranged over by $A, B,$

etc.) and \mathcal{M} be a set of *messages* (ranged over by \mathbf{m} , \mathbf{x} , etc.). We take \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{M} disjoint. Let

$$\mathcal{C} = (\mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{P}) \setminus \{(A, A) \mid A \in \mathcal{P}\} \quad \mathcal{L}^! = \mathcal{C} \times \{!\} \times \mathcal{M} \quad \mathcal{L}^? = \mathcal{C} \times \{?\} \times \mathcal{M}$$

be the sets of *channels*, output labels, and input labels respectively. We write $AB!m \in \mathcal{L}^!$ instead of $((A, B), !, m) \in \mathcal{L}^!$, to mean that A sends m to B ; we write $AB?m \in \mathcal{L}^?$ instead of $((A, B), ?, m) \in \mathcal{L}^?$, to mean that B receives m from A . Notice that, in the asynchronous setting, sending and receiving a message are distinct actions. The elements of $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}^! \cup \mathcal{L}^?$ (ranged over by l) will be used to label the events of our event structures. The *subject* of a label l , written $\text{subj}(l)$, is defined as $\text{subj}(AB!m) = \text{subj}(BA?m) = A$. The *co-action* of $l \in \mathcal{L}$ is defined as $\text{co}(AB!m) = AB?m$ and $\text{co}(AB?m) = AB!m$ and extends element-wise on sets of actions.

Definition 1 (Event structures). *An event structure labelled over \mathcal{L} (shortly event structure) is a tuple $\mathcal{E} = (E, \leq, \#, \lambda)$ where*

- E a set of events
- $\leq \subseteq E \times E$ a partial order, the causality relation
- $\# \subseteq E \times E$ a symmetric and irreflexive relation, the conflict relation,
- $\lambda : E \rightarrow \mathcal{L}$ a labelling mapping.

are such that

- each event has only finitely many predecessors, namely $\forall e \in E. \{e' \in E \mid e' \leq e\}$ is finite, and
- conflicts are hereditary, namely $\forall e, e', e'' \in E. e \# e' \ \& \ e' \leq e'' \implies e \# e''$

If $\mathcal{E} = (E, \leq, \#, \lambda)$ is an event structure then $\min(\mathcal{E}), \max(\mathcal{E}) \subseteq E$ are the minimal and the maximal elements in the poset (E, \leq) . We say that $e, e' \in E$ are independent (in \mathcal{E}) if $\{(e, e'), (e', e)\} \cap (\leq \cup \#) = \emptyset$ (namely, e and e' are not in conflict and there is no causal relation between them). We define $\epsilon = (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset)$ as the empty event structure, where $\lambda_\emptyset = \emptyset$ is the empty mapping.

Notice that if $\mathcal{E} \neq \epsilon$ then minimal elements do exist, while this is not necessarily the case for maximal ones. We depict event structures following the customary representation of the literature [9] as the diagram (5) below; instead of events though, we prefer to use their labels, for instance:

120 represents an event structure with events e_1, \dots, e_7 (not represented in the di-
 121 agram above) and labelled respectively by l_1, \dots, l_7 where

- 122 • the event e_1 precedes e_2 (i.e., $e_1 \leq e_2$ in the partial order of the event
 structure)
- 124 • events e_1 and e_3 are in conflict; recall that the conflict relation is heredi-
 tary, hence e_1 and e_2 are in conflict with all other events but e_7
- 126 • events e_2 and e_6 are maximal; the latter follows both e_5 and e_7
- events e_5 and e_7 are independent of each other (actually, e_7 is independent
 of any event but e_6).

128 In our diagrams we adopt the implicit assumption that each occurrence of a
 129 label corresponds to a different event; for instance, in the diagram (5), even if
 130 two labels, say l_1 and l_7 were equal, the corresponding events would be distinct
 (i.e., $e_1 \neq e_7$).

132 An event structure induces a natural order and conflict relations on the
 events performed by each participant. More precisely, the *projection* of an event
 134 structure $\mathcal{E} = (E, \leq, \#, \lambda)$ on a participant $A \in \mathcal{P}$ is the structure

$$\mathcal{E} \upharpoonright A = (E \upharpoonright A, \leq \upharpoonright A, \# \upharpoonright A, \lambda \upharpoonright A)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} 136 \quad E \upharpoonright A &= \{e \in E \mid \text{sbj}(\lambda(e)) = A\} \\ &\leq \upharpoonright A = \{(e, e') \in E \upharpoonright A \times E \upharpoonright A \mid e \leq e'\} \\ 138 \quad \# \upharpoonright A &= \{(e, e') \in E \upharpoonright A \times E \upharpoonright A \mid e \# e'\} \\ \lambda \upharpoonright A &= \lambda|_{E \upharpoonright A}, \text{ namely the restriction of } \lambda \text{ to } E \upharpoonright A \end{aligned}$$

140 Trivially, the induced relations form an event structure.

Lemma 2. *If \mathcal{E} is an event structure and $A \in \mathcal{P}$ then $\mathcal{E} \upharpoonright A$ is an event structure.*

142 *Proof.* Immediate since projections of order (resp. conflict) relation on a partic-
 ipant A yields a subset of \leq (resp. $\#$); formally $\leq \upharpoonright A \subseteq \leq$ and $\# \upharpoonright A \subseteq \#$. \square

144 We now define a few operations instrumental to our technical development.
 Let $\mathcal{E}_0 = (E_0, \leq_0, \#_0, \lambda_0)$ and $\mathcal{E}_1 = (E_1, \leq_1, \#_1, \lambda_1)$ be labelled event structures.

146 The product operation $_ \otimes _$ yields the disjoint union of event structures
 preserving their orders, conflicts, and labellings; it is define as

$$\mathcal{E}_0 \otimes \mathcal{E}_1 = (E_0 \uplus E_1, \leq, \#, \lambda)$$

148 where writing $\iota_i : E_i \rightarrow E_0 \uplus E_1$ for the injections, we set

$$\iota_i e \leq \iota_j e' \iff i = j \ \& \ e \leq_i e' \quad \iota_i e \# \iota_j e' \iff i = j \ \& \ e \#_i e' \quad \lambda(\iota_i e) = \lambda_i(e)$$

The sum $\sum_{i \in I} \mathcal{E}_i$ yields the disjoint union of a family $\{\mathcal{E}_i\}_{i \in I}$ of event structures
150 $\mathcal{E}_i = (\mathbf{E}_i, \leq_i, \#_i, \lambda_i)$ preserving their orders and labellings while introducing
conflicts among events of different members of the family; it is defined as the
152 event structure $(\bigsqcup_{i \in I} \mathbf{E}_i, \leq, \#, \lambda)$ where, writing $\iota_i : \mathbf{E}_i \rightarrow \bigsqcup_{i \in I} \mathbf{E}_i$ for the
injections, the following hold:

$$\iota_i e \leq \iota_j e' \iff i = j \ \& \ e \leq_i e' \quad \iota_i e \# \iota_j e' \iff i \neq j \vee (i = j \ \& \ e \#_i e') \quad \lambda(\iota_i e) = \lambda_i(e)$$

154 In particular we write

$$\mathcal{E}_0 + \mathcal{E}_1 = \sum_{i \in \{0,1\}} \mathcal{E}_i \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i \in I} \mathcal{E} = \sum_{i \in I} \mathcal{E}_i \quad \text{where } \mathcal{E}_i = \mathcal{E} \text{ for all } i \in I$$

Lemma 3. *If $\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{E}_1$ are event structures and $\{\mathcal{E}_i\}_{i \in I}$ is a family of event struc-*
156 *tures then*

$$\mathcal{E}_0 \otimes \mathcal{E}_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i \in I} \mathcal{E}_i \quad \text{are event structures.}$$

Definition 4 (Configuration domain). *Let $\mathcal{E} = (\mathbf{E}, \leq, \#, \lambda)$ be an event struc-*
158 *ture. A set of events $x \subseteq \mathbf{E}$ is a configuration of \mathcal{E} if*

1. $e \leq e' \ \& \ e' \in x \implies e \in x$ (*x is downward closed*)
- 160 2. $\forall e, e' \in x. \neg(e \# e')$ (*x is consistent*)

Let $C = \{x \subseteq \mathbf{E} \mid x \text{ a configuration}\}$; the domain of configurations of \mathcal{E} is the
162 *poset $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{E}) = (C, \subseteq)$. We say that $x \in C$ is maximal if it is such in $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{E})$:*
 $\mathcal{C}_{\max}(\mathcal{E})$ *is the set of maximal configurations.*

164 Being conflict-free and maximal, configurations in $\mathcal{C}_{\max}(\mathcal{E})$ correspond to
branches of events of \mathcal{E} .

166 3. Well-formedness by Typing

We formalise global views of choreographies as g-choreographies [8, 7]. Al-
168 though we maintain the original syntax, we provide a new semantics of g-
choreographies based on event structures. This is instrumental to identify a
170 simple notion of well-formedness that can be statically checked.

3.1. Global Choreographies

172 Definition 5 introduces *global choreographies*. The syntax of a g-choreography
is given by the grammar below that we borrow from [7].

174 **Definition 5** (Global Choreographies). *The set \mathcal{G} of global choreographies (g-choreographies for short) consists of the terms G derived by the grammar*

$$G ::= \mathbf{0} \qquad \text{empty} \qquad (6)$$

$$\mid A \xrightarrow{m} B \qquad \text{interaction} \qquad (7)$$

$$\mid G; G' \qquad \text{sequential} \qquad (8)$$

$$\mid G \mid G' \qquad \text{parallel} \qquad (9)$$

$$\mid G + G' \qquad \text{choice} \qquad (10)$$

176 such that $A \neq B$ in interactions (7). We let $\mathcal{P}(G)$ be the set of participants occurring in G .

178 Besides the empty choreography $\mathbf{0}$, the syntax of Definition 5 allows us to specify choreographies whose basic elements are interactions $A \xrightarrow{m} B$ which represent that participant A sends message m to participant B , which in turn should receive it. Finally, g-choreographies can be composed sequentially, in parallel, and non-deterministically. The syntax in [7] encompasses iterative g-choreographies which we drop for simplicity. We conjecture that adding iteration can be done following standard techniques at the cost of a substantial increase of the technical complexity.

Example 6. *The term in (4) in Section 1 is a g-choreography. \diamond*

186 We now give the semantics of g-choreographies in terms of event structures. To this purpose, note that not every G is “meaningful” because G can specify protocols where the behaviour of some participants, say B , depends on choices made by others that are not properly propagated to B . The following example illustrates this.

Example 7. *The g-choreography $G = A \xrightarrow{m} C; B \xrightarrow{m} C + A \xrightarrow{n} C; B \xrightarrow{n} C$ specifies a protocol where A decides whether to send m or n to C . In either case, B should mimic A and send the same message to C . However, in a distributed implementation of this protocol B is oblivious of the decision of A ; hence, e.g., B could send message m while A decided to send message n . \diamond*

192 To mitigate the problem above, we give *well-formedness* conditions that rule out meaningless g-choreographies. We start with *well-branchedness* which requires that

- 194 • the minimal events of each participant have distinct labels if they are in conflict and
- 196 • all participants can ascertain which branch the system is selecting (*awareness*); more precisely, there is a participant that resolves the choice by performing distinct outputs as first communications while the communications (if any) of any other participant are inputs.

200 This is formalised in the next definition.

Definition 8 (Well-branchedness). *Event structures \mathcal{E}_0 and \mathcal{E}_1 are well-branched (in symbols $wb(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{E}_1)$) if, for $\mathcal{E} = \mathcal{E}_0 + \mathcal{E}_1 = (E, \leq, \#, \lambda)$, the following two conditions hold:*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{determinacy: } & \forall \mathbf{B} \in \mathcal{P} : (\mathcal{E}_0 \upharpoonright \mathbf{B} = \epsilon \iff \mathcal{E}_1 \upharpoonright \mathbf{B} = \epsilon) \ \& \\ & \forall e, e' \in \min(E \upharpoonright \mathbf{B}) : e \# e' \implies \lambda(e) \neq \lambda(e') \\ \text{awareness: } & \exists \mathbf{A} \in \mathcal{P} : \emptyset \neq \lambda(\min(E \upharpoonright \mathbf{A})) \subseteq \{l \in \mathcal{L}^! \mid \text{subj}(l) = \mathbf{A}\} \ \& \\ & \forall \mathbf{B} \neq \mathbf{A} \in \mathcal{P} : \lambda(\min(E \upharpoonright \mathbf{B})) \subseteq \{l \in \mathcal{L}^? \mid \text{subj}(l) = \mathbf{B}\} \end{aligned}$$

We dub active the unique participant \mathbf{A} satisfying the second condition and passive the others.

Well-branchedness is akin to the conditions on behavioural types that enforce distributed consensus. Namely, each choice is determined by a unique (active) participant which starts to send messages to passive participants, which can discriminate about the branch taken from of the messages they receive.

As well-branchedness, the parallel composition of g-choreographies is subject to some conditions. As observed in [7], “confusion” may arise when different threads of participants exchange the same message: the message meant to be received by a thread is received by the other. If this happens there is a violation of the causal order of the events. We re-cast the notion of *well-forkedness* in [7] in terms of event structures.

Definition 9 (Well-forkedness). *Two event structures $\mathcal{E} = (E, \leq, \#, \lambda)$ and $\mathcal{E}' = (E', \leq, \#', \lambda')$ are well-forked (in symbols $wf(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{E}')$) if $\lambda(E) \cap \lambda'(E') = \emptyset$.*

The next example illustrates the effect of violating well-forkedness.

Example 10. *The g-choreography $A \xrightarrow{m} B; B \xrightarrow{m} C \mid A \xrightarrow{m} B; B \xrightarrow{n} D$ is not well-forked because the interaction between B and C should start after the “left thread” of A had sent message m . However, it could happen that the left thread of B receives the message sent by the right thread of A so violating the specification. And likewise for the “right threads”. \diamond*

Definition 11 (Sequential composition). *Let $\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{E}'$ be event structures and*

$$(E'', \leq'', \#'', \lambda'') = \mathcal{E} \otimes \sum_{x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\mathcal{E})} \mathcal{E}'_x$$

where the structures $\mathcal{E}'_x = (E_x, \leq_x, \#_x, \lambda_x)$ are disjoint copies of \mathcal{E}' , then

$$\text{seq}(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{E}') = (E'', \leq'' \cup \bigcup_{x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\mathcal{E})} \{(e, e') \in x \times E_x \mid \text{subj}(\lambda''(e)) = \text{subj}(\lambda''(e'))\}, \#'', \lambda'').$$

The intuition of the definition of $\text{seq}(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{E}')$ is that any branch $x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\mathcal{E})$ of \mathcal{E} is concatenated to a (pairwise incompatible) copy of \mathcal{E}'_x , where events in \mathcal{E} cause those of \mathcal{E}'_x with labels having the same subject. Admittedly, this is unnecessarily abstract in respect to the semantics of g-choreographies given below (cf.

Definition 13) since an event structure \mathcal{E} interpreting a g-choreography is finite,
 226 and hence $\mathcal{C}_{\max}(\mathcal{E})$ and any of its elements are such: hence any $x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\mathcal{E})$
 includes a finite subset of maximal events with respect to $\leq_{\mathcal{E}}$. However the
 228 definition applies to infinite structures as well.

Lemma 12. *If $\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{E}'$ are event structures, then $\text{seq}(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{E}')$ is an event structure.*

230 We can now give a denotational semantics of g-choreographies. We require
 our semantics to be defined only on g-choreographies amenable of being realised
 232 by distributed components satisfying the following requirements:

- no extra components: each component uniquely corresponds to a partici-
 234 pant of the g-choreography
- no extra communications: each communication among the components
 236 uniquely corresponds to some communication events of the (semantics of
 the) g-choreography

238 These requirements impose that the communication behaviour of a realisa-
 tion of a g-choreography faithfully reflects the communication events of the
 240 g-choreography.

Definition 13 (Semantics). *Let G be a g-choreography. The semantics $\llbracket G \rrbracket$
 242 of G is the partial mapping assigning an event structure to G according to the
 following inductive clauses:*

$$\begin{aligned}
 \llbracket \mathbf{0} \rrbracket &= \epsilon \\
 \llbracket A \xrightarrow{m} B \rrbracket &= (\{e_1, e_2\}, \{e_1 < e_2\}, \emptyset, \{e_1 \mapsto AB!m, e_2 \mapsto AB?m\}) \\
 \llbracket G; G' \rrbracket &= \text{seq}(\llbracket G \rrbracket, \llbracket G' \rrbracket) \\
 \llbracket G \mid G' \rrbracket &= \begin{cases} \llbracket G \rrbracket \otimes \llbracket G' \rrbracket & \text{if } wf(\llbracket G \rrbracket, \llbracket G' \rrbracket) \\ \perp & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\
 \llbracket G + G' \rrbracket &= \begin{cases} \llbracket G \rrbracket + \llbracket G' \rrbracket & \text{if } wb(\llbracket G \rrbracket, \llbracket G' \rrbracket) \\ \perp & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

244 where if either $\llbracket G \rrbracket$ or $\llbracket G' \rrbracket$ is \perp , then $\text{seq}(\llbracket G \rrbracket, \llbracket G' \rrbracket)$, $\llbracket G \rrbracket \otimes \llbracket G' \rrbracket$ and $\llbracket G \rrbracket + \llbracket G' \rrbracket$
 are all equal to \perp . A g-choreography G is well-formed if $\llbracket G \rrbracket \neq \perp$.

246 We say that a g-choreography G is *well-formed* when each choice subterm of
 G is well-branched and each parallel subterm of G is well-forked.

248 **Example 14.** *Let us spell out the semantics of the g-choreography*

$$G = C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S + C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S; S \xrightarrow{\text{stats}} C; S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C$$

obtained by the refinement (3) (cf. Section 1) with the further refinement of
 250 $C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S$ with its ground counterpart $C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S$. By Definition 13, $\llbracket G \rrbracket$ is defined

252 if $wb(\llbracket C \xrightarrow{md} S \rrbracket, \llbracket C \xrightarrow{req} S; S \xrightarrow{stats} C; S \xrightarrow{done} C \rrbracket)$ holds. We now verify that this is the case. By definition, we have:

254 The sum operation on event structures introduces conflicts between the events in $\llbracket C \xrightarrow{md} S \rrbracket$ and those in $\llbracket C \xrightarrow{req} S; S \xrightarrow{stats} C; S \xrightarrow{done} C \rrbracket$, hence:

256 (recall that conflicts are hereditary, hence it is enough to put only minimal events in conflict). Now we look at the projections on C and on S of \mathcal{E} :

where in $\mathcal{E} \upharpoonright C$ the minimal events are in conflict because they are in conflict in \mathcal{E} by construction and in $\llbracket \mathcal{E} \rrbracket \upharpoonright S$ they are in conflict because in \mathcal{E} the events inherit previous conflict. It is easy to verify that the conditions of Definition 8 are therefore verified. \diamond

258 **Example 15.** Recall the g -choreography (4) in Section 1 which we rewrite as $G_{err} = G + G'$ where

$$G = C \xrightarrow{md} B; B \xrightarrow{md} S \quad \text{and} \quad G' = C \xrightarrow{req} S; S \xrightarrow{done} C$$

Let us show that $\llbracket G_{err} \rrbracket = \perp$. In fact,

It is easy to check that the determinacy condition of Definition 8 does not hold for \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{S} because $\llbracket \mathbf{G} \rrbracket \upharpoonright \mathbf{B} \neq \epsilon$ while $\llbracket \mathbf{G}' \rrbracket \upharpoonright \mathbf{B} = \epsilon$ and likewise for \mathbf{S} . \diamond

260 3.2. Typing well-formedness

By Definition 13, ill-formed g-choreographies \mathbf{G} are meaningless, i.e. $\llbracket \mathbf{G} \rrbracket = \perp$. However, it is too expensive to check that $\llbracket \mathbf{G} \rrbracket \neq \perp$ via a direct inspection of the event structure $\llbracket \mathbf{G} \rrbracket$. Also, it is hard to see how to extend the semantics to refinable communications, as their intended meaning is an infinite set of possible realisations by concrete g-choreographies. To circumvent this difficulty we formalise sufficient conditions for well-formedness via a typing system.

Our typing discipline assigns to a g-choreography type $\langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ where $\phi \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ and $\Lambda \subseteq \mathcal{L}$. Intuitively, ϕ and Λ are respectively the labels of minimal and maximal events of each participant in the g-choreography. Our judgements take the form

$$\Pi \vdash \mathbf{G} : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$$

and their intended meaning is: the g-choreography \mathbf{G} has a defined semantics and it has type $\langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ under the assumption that its participants are those in $\Pi \subseteq \mathcal{P}$. It is convenient to introduce the mapping $\hat{\cdot} : 2^{\mathcal{L}} \rightarrow \mathcal{P} \rightarrow 2^{\mathcal{L}}$ defined as $\hat{L}(\mathbf{A}) = \{l \in L \mid \text{subj}(l) = \mathbf{A}\}$. Then

$$L = \bigcup_{\mathbf{A} \in \mathcal{P}} \hat{L}(\mathbf{A})$$

so that we can see any $L \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ as a family of sets of (labels of) actions indexed over \mathcal{P} . Note that if L is finite then $\hat{L}(\mathbf{A}) \neq \emptyset$ for finitely many participants $\mathbf{A} \in \mathcal{P}$.

Remark 16. We could avoid the use of the context Π in judgements; we however prefer to explicitly list relevant participants for clarity.

The typing judgments are derived by the rules in Fig. 1, defining a type system which we dub \mathcal{G} . In the conclusion of rule T-SEQ, for $L \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ and $\Pi \subseteq \mathcal{P}$ we write $L - \Pi = \{l \in L \mid \text{subj}(l) \notin \Pi\}$. Two sets of labels $U, V \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ are *output uniform* if $U \cap V = \emptyset$ and $U \cup V \subseteq \mathcal{L}^!$; likewise, U and V are *input uniform* if $U \cap V = \emptyset$ and $U \cup V \subseteq \mathcal{L}^?$. The side condition $\phi_1 \bowtie_{\Pi} \phi_2$ in rule T-CH is defined by the clauses:

- 286 1. *Active*: there is a unique $\mathbf{A} \in \Pi$ such that $\hat{\phi}_1(\mathbf{A})$ and $\hat{\phi}_2(\mathbf{A})$ are output uniform and both non-empty.
- 288 2. *Passive*: for all $\mathbf{B} \neq \mathbf{A} \in \Pi$, $\hat{\phi}_1(\mathbf{B})$ and $\hat{\phi}_2(\mathbf{B})$ are input uniform and $\hat{\phi}_1(\mathbf{B}) = \emptyset$ if and only if $\hat{\phi}_2(\mathbf{B}) = \emptyset$.

290 Note that conditions (1) and (2) above imply the uniqueness of active participants.

292 Now we can formally state the correctness of system \mathcal{G} with respect to the intended meaning of the typing judgements:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\emptyset \vdash \mathbf{0} : \langle \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle} \text{T-END} \qquad \frac{\phi = \Lambda = \{A B!m, A B?m\}}{\{A, B\} \vdash A \xrightarrow{m} B : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle} \text{T-INT} \\
\\
\frac{\Pi_1 \vdash G_1 : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle \quad \Pi_2 \vdash G_2 : \langle \phi_2, \Lambda_2 \rangle}{\Pi_1 \cup \Pi_2 \vdash G_1; G_2 : \langle \phi_1 \cup (\phi_2 - \Pi_1), \Lambda_2 \cup (\Lambda_1 - \Pi_2) \rangle} \text{T-SEQ} \\
\\
\frac{\Pi_1 \vdash G_1 : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle \quad \Pi_2 \vdash G_2 : \langle \phi_2, \Lambda_2 \rangle \quad \Pi_1 \cap \Pi_2 = \emptyset}{\Pi_1 \cup \Pi_2 \vdash G_1 \mid G_2 : \langle \phi_1 \cup \phi_2, \Lambda_1 \cup \Lambda_2 \rangle} \text{T-PAR} \\
\\
\frac{\Pi \vdash G_1 : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle \quad \Pi \vdash G_2 : \langle \phi_2, \Lambda_2 \rangle \quad \phi_1 \bowtie_{\Pi} \phi_2}{\Pi \vdash G_1 + G_2 : \langle \phi_1 \cup \phi_2, \Lambda_1 \cup \Lambda_2 \rangle} \text{T-CH}
\end{array}$$

Figure 1: System \mathcal{G} : typing rules for g-choreographies

294 **Theorem 17** (Correctness). *If $\Pi \vdash G : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ is derivable then $\llbracket G \rrbracket \neq \perp$, $\Pi = \mathcal{P}(G)$, and*

$$\widehat{\phi}(A) = \min(\llbracket G \rrbracket \upharpoonright A) \quad \text{and} \quad \widehat{\Lambda}(A) = \max(\llbracket G \rrbracket \upharpoonright A)$$

296 *hold for all $A \in \Pi$.*

Proof. By induction over derivations. In case the derivation ends by rule T-END
298 the thesis is immediate. We treat in detail the other cases.

CASE T-INT. By inspecting the rule for interaction:

$$\frac{\phi = \Lambda = \{A B!m, A B?m\}}{\{A, B\} \vdash A \xrightarrow{m} B : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle} \text{T-INT}$$

300 we see ¹ that $\{A, B\} = \mathcal{P}(A \xrightarrow{m} B)$; also we know that $A \xrightarrow{m} B$ has a defined semantics:

$$\llbracket A \xrightarrow{m} B \rrbracket = (\{e_1, e_2\}, \{e_1 < e_2\}, \emptyset, \{e_1 \mapsto A B!m, e_2 \mapsto B A?m\})$$

$$\text{hence} \quad \widehat{\phi}(A) = \widehat{\Lambda}(A) = \{A B!m\} = \min(\llbracket A \xrightarrow{m} B \rrbracket \upharpoonright A) = \max(\llbracket A \xrightarrow{m} B \rrbracket \upharpoonright A)$$

$$\text{and} \quad \widehat{\phi}(A) = \widehat{\Lambda}(B) = \{B A?m\} = \min(\llbracket A \xrightarrow{m} B \rrbracket \upharpoonright B) = \max(\llbracket A \xrightarrow{m} B \rrbracket \upharpoonright B)$$

302 The distinction among minimal and maximal elements in a singleton poset is clearly immaterial; it becomes relevant in case of the subsequent rules.

¹Recall that $\mathcal{P}(G)$ are the participants occurring in G

304 CASE T-SEQ. Sequential composition of g-choreography is typed by rule:

$$\frac{\Pi_1 \vdash \mathbf{G}_1 : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle \quad \Pi_2 \vdash \mathbf{G}_2 : \langle \phi_2, \Lambda_2 \rangle}{\Pi_1 \cup \Pi_2 \vdash \mathbf{G}_1; \mathbf{G}_2 : \langle \phi_1 \cup (\phi_2 - \Pi_1), \Lambda_2 \cup (\Lambda_1 - \Pi_2) \rangle} \text{T-SEQ}$$

By induction $\llbracket \mathbf{G}_i \rrbracket = \mathcal{E}_i \neq \perp$ for $i = 1, 2$, hence $\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1; \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket = \text{seq}(\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1 \rrbracket, \llbracket \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket)$ is defined. Let $\mathcal{E}_i = \llbracket \mathbf{G}_i \rrbracket$ and $\{\mathcal{E}_x\}_{x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\mathcal{E}_1)}$ a $\mathcal{C}_{\max}(\mathcal{E}_1)$ -indexed family of pairwise disjoint copies of \mathcal{E}_1 namely, for each maximal configuration $x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\mathcal{E}_1)$ of \mathcal{E}_1 , the structure \mathcal{E}_x is isomorphic to \mathcal{E}_2 and $E_x \cap E_y = \emptyset$ for all $y \neq x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\mathcal{E}_1)$. Then by definition, the order relation \leq_{seq} of $\text{seq}(\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1 \rrbracket, \llbracket \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket)$ is the relation;

$$\leq_1 \cup \bigcup_{x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\mathcal{E}_1)} (\leq_x \cup \{(e, e') \in x \times E_x \mid \text{sbj}(\lambda_1(e)) = \text{sbj}(\lambda_x(e'))\})$$

310 where \leq_x is the order relation of \mathcal{E}_x , and $\lambda_x(e') = \lambda_2(e')$ by construction. If e is minimal with respect to \leq_{seq} then either it is such with respect to \leq_1 , or $e \in E_x$ is minimal with respect to \leq_x and therefore $\text{sbj}(\lambda_1(e')) \neq \text{sbj}(\lambda_x(e))$ for all maximal $e' \in E_1$. If we consider the projection $\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1; \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket \upharpoonright \mathbf{A}$ for any participant \mathbf{A} of $\mathbf{G}_1; \mathbf{G}_2$, then by definition all event labels have the same subject \mathbf{A} . So, if $\mathbf{A} \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{G}_1)$ then each maximal configuration of $\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1 \rrbracket$ has an event whose label has subject \mathbf{A} , hence $\min(\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1; \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket \upharpoonright \mathbf{A})$ are exactly the minimal events in $\min(\mathcal{E}_1 \upharpoonright \mathbf{A})$. Otherwise, $\min(\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1; \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket \upharpoonright \mathbf{A}) = \min(\mathcal{E}_2 \upharpoonright \mathbf{A})$. By induction we know that for $i = 1, 2$ it holds $\Pi_i = \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{G}_i)$ and $\widehat{\phi}_i(\mathbf{A}) = \min(\mathcal{E}_i \upharpoonright \mathbf{A})$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \min(\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1; \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket \upharpoonright \mathbf{A}) &= \min(\mathcal{E}_1 \upharpoonright \mathbf{A}) \cup \{e \in \min(\mathcal{E}_2 \upharpoonright \mathbf{A}) \mid \mathbf{A} \notin \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{G}_1)\} \\ &= \widehat{\phi}_1(\mathbf{A}) \cup (\widehat{\phi}_2 - \widehat{\Pi}_1(\mathbf{A})) \\ &= (\phi_1 \cup (\phi_2 - \Pi_1))(\mathbf{A}) \end{aligned}$$

where of course either $\widehat{\phi}_1(\mathbf{A})$ or $\widehat{\phi}_2 - \widehat{\Pi}_1(\mathbf{A})$ must be empty. Similarly we get $(\Lambda_2 \cup (\Lambda_1 - \Pi_2))(\mathbf{A}) = \max(\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1; \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket \upharpoonright \mathbf{A})$.

CASE T-PAR. The rule is:

$$\frac{\Pi_1 \vdash \mathbf{G}_1 : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle \quad \Pi_2 \vdash \mathbf{G}_2 : \langle \phi_2, \Lambda_2 \rangle \quad \Pi_1 \cap \Pi_2 = \emptyset}{\Pi_1 \cup \Pi_2 \vdash \mathbf{G}_1 \mid \mathbf{G}_2 : \langle \phi_1 \cup \phi_2, \Lambda_1 \cup \Lambda_2 \rangle} \text{T-PAR}$$

322 By induction, for $i = 1, 2$ we have $\Pi_i = \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{G}_i)$ and $\llbracket \mathbf{G}_i \rrbracket = \mathcal{E}_i \neq \perp$. Hence, the condition $\Pi_1 \cap \Pi_2 = \emptyset$ implies that $\lambda_1(E_1) \cap \lambda_2(E_2) = \emptyset$, where E_i and λ_i are the carrier and the labeling mapping of \mathcal{E}_i respectively, so that $\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1 \mid \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket = \llbracket \mathbf{G}_1 \rrbracket \otimes \llbracket \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket$ is defined. Again by induction, for all participants \mathbf{A} of \mathbf{G}_i for $i = 1, 2$ we have that:

$$\widehat{\phi}_i(\mathbf{A}) = \min(\llbracket \mathbf{G}_i \rrbracket \upharpoonright \mathbf{A}) \quad \text{and} \quad \widehat{\Lambda}_i(\mathbf{A}) = \max(\llbracket \mathbf{G}_i \rrbracket \upharpoonright \mathbf{A})$$

328 By definition of the product operation, we know that $\leq_{\mathcal{E}_1 \otimes \mathcal{E}_2}$ is just $\leq_{\mathcal{E}_1} \cup \leq_{\mathcal{E}_2}$, which is a disjoint union (and the same holds of the $\#_{\mathcal{E}_1 \otimes \mathcal{E}_2}$ relation). Observing that

$$\widehat{\phi}_1 \cup \widehat{\phi}_2(\mathbf{A}) = \{l \in \phi_1 \cup \phi_2 \mid \text{sbj}(l) = \mathbf{A}\} = \{l \in \phi_1 \mid \text{sbj}(l) = \mathbf{A}\} \cup \{l \in \phi_2 \mid \text{sbj}(l) = \mathbf{A}\} = \widehat{\phi}_1(\mathbf{A}) \cup \widehat{\phi}_2(\mathbf{A})$$

330 and similarly that $\widehat{\Lambda_1 \cup \Lambda_2}(\mathbf{A}) = \widehat{\Lambda_1}(\mathbf{A}) \cup \widehat{\Lambda_2}(\mathbf{A})$, we conclude that, for all participants \mathbf{A} of $\mathbf{G}_1 \mid \mathbf{G}_2$:

$$\widehat{\phi_1 \cup \phi_2}(\mathbf{A}) = \min(\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1 \mid \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket \upharpoonright \mathbf{A}) \quad \text{and} \quad \widehat{\Lambda_1 \cup \Lambda_2}(\mathbf{A}) = \max(\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1 \mid \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket \upharpoonright \mathbf{A}).$$

332

CASE T-CH. Then the rule for typing choice is:

$$\frac{\Pi \vdash \mathbf{G}_1 : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle \quad \Pi \vdash \mathbf{G}_2 : \langle \phi_2, \Lambda_2 \rangle \quad \phi_1 \bowtie_{\Pi} \phi_2}{\Pi \vdash \mathbf{G}_1 + \mathbf{G}_2 : \langle \phi_1 \cup \phi_2, \Lambda_1 \cup \Lambda_2 \rangle} \text{T-CH}$$

334 By induction, for $i = 1, 2$ we have that $\llbracket \mathbf{G}_i \rrbracket \neq \perp$, the participants of \mathbf{G}_i are Π , and that $\widehat{\phi}_i(\mathbf{R}) = \min(\mathcal{E}_i \upharpoonright \mathbf{R})$ and $\widehat{\Lambda}_i(\mathbf{R}) = \max(\mathcal{E}_i \upharpoonright \mathbf{R})$ for all $\mathbf{R} \in \Pi$. Let
 336 $\llbracket \mathbf{G}_i \rrbracket = \mathcal{E}_i = (\mathbf{E}_i, \leq_i, \#_i, \lambda_i)$ and $\mathcal{E} = \mathcal{E}_0 + \mathcal{E}_1$. By condition 1 in the definition of $\phi_1 \bowtie_{\Pi} \phi_2$, and remembering the identification of e with $\lambda_i(e)$, we have that
 338 $\widehat{\phi}_i(\mathbf{A}) = \min(\mathcal{E}_i \upharpoonright \mathbf{A}) \neq \emptyset$ for both $i = 1, 2$, so that $\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{E}_1 \neq \epsilon$.

Again by 1, we know that \mathbf{A} is active in both \mathcal{E}_i , since $\min(\mathcal{E}_1 \upharpoonright \mathbf{A})$ and
 340 $\min(\mathcal{E}_2 \upharpoonright \mathbf{A})$ are output uniform, while condition 2 in the definition of $\phi_1 \bowtie_{\Pi} \phi_2$ implies that all $\mathbf{B} \in \Pi \setminus \mathbf{A}$ are passive, since $\min(\mathcal{E}_i \upharpoonright \mathbf{B})$ are input uniform. We
 342 conclude that $wb(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{E}_1)$ and hence that $\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1 + \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket \neq \perp$. Also, $\widehat{\phi_1 \cup \phi_2}(\mathbf{R}) = \min(\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1 + \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket \upharpoonright \mathbf{R})$ and $\widehat{\Lambda_1 \cup \Lambda_2}(\mathbf{R}) = \max(\llbracket \mathbf{G}_1 + \mathbf{G}_2 \rrbracket \upharpoonright \mathbf{R})$ for all $\mathbf{R} \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{G}_1 + \mathbf{G}_2)$
 344 follows by induction. □

346 **Corollary 18.** *If \mathbf{G} is a typable g -choreography then \mathbf{G} is well-formed. Moreover a typable \mathbf{G} has exactly one typing $\Pi \vdash \mathbf{G} : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$.*

348 To further illustrate the rules of system \mathcal{G} , we exemplify their usage.

Example 19. *Consider typing $\mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{req}} \mathbf{S}; \mathbf{S} \xrightarrow{\text{done}} \mathbf{C}$; then we have:*

$$\frac{\phi_1 = \Lambda_1 = \{\mathbf{CS!req}, \mathbf{CS?req}\} \quad \phi_2 = \Lambda_2 = \{\mathbf{SC!done}, \mathbf{SC?done}\}}{\frac{\{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\} \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{req}} \mathbf{S} : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle \quad \{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\} \vdash \mathbf{S} \xrightarrow{\text{done}} \mathbf{C} : \langle \phi_2, \Lambda_2 \rangle}{\{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\} \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{req}} \mathbf{S}; \mathbf{S} \xrightarrow{\text{done}} \mathbf{C} : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_2 \rangle}}$$

350 because $\{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\} \cup \{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\} = \{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\}$, $\phi_1 \cup (\phi_2 - \{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\}) = \phi_1$ since $\phi_2 - \{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\} = \emptyset$, and $\Lambda_2 \cup (\Lambda_1 - \{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\}) = \Lambda_2$ as $\Lambda_1 - \{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\} = \emptyset$. Similarly, taking

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_5 = \phi_3 \cup (\phi_4 - \{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{B}\}) &= \phi_3 \cup \{\mathbf{BS?md}\} &= \{\mathbf{CB!md}, \mathbf{CB?md}, \mathbf{BS?md}\} &\text{ and} \\ \Lambda_5 = \Lambda_4 \cup (\Lambda_3 - \{\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{S}\}) &= \Lambda_4 \cup \{\mathbf{CB!md}\} &= \{\mathbf{CB!md}, \mathbf{BS!md}, \mathbf{BS?md}\} \end{aligned}$$

352 then

$$\frac{\phi_3 = \Lambda_3 = \{\mathbf{CB!md}, \mathbf{CB?md}\} \quad \phi_4 = \Lambda_4 = \{\mathbf{BS!md}, \mathbf{BS?md}\}}{\frac{\{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{B}\} \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{B} : \langle \phi_3, \Lambda_3 \rangle \quad \{\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{S}\} \vdash \mathbf{S} \xrightarrow{\text{done}} \mathbf{C} : \langle \phi_4, \Lambda_4 \rangle}{\{\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\} \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{B}; \mathbf{B} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{S} : \langle \phi_5, \Lambda_5 \rangle}}$$

is the typing of $C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} B; B \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S$ we obtain: \diamond

Example 20. By rule T-CH we can type e.g.

$$\frac{\phi_1 = \Lambda_1 = \{CS!req, CS?req\} \quad \phi_6 = \Lambda_6 = \{CS!done, CS?done\}}{\{C, S\} \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle \quad \{C, S\} \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{done}} S : \langle \phi_6, \Lambda_6 \rangle} \quad \phi_1 \bowtie_{\{C, S\}} \phi_6$$

$$\{C, S\} \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S + C \xrightarrow{\text{done}} S : \langle \phi_1 \cup \phi_6, \Lambda_1 \cup \Lambda_6 \rangle$$

354 in fact, $\phi_1 \bowtie_{\{C, S\}} \phi_6$ holds, being C the unique participant in $\{C, S\}$ such that
 $\widehat{\phi}_1(C)$ and $\widehat{\phi}_6(C)$ are output uniform, and the remaining S is such that $\widehat{\phi}_1(S)$
 356 and $\widehat{\phi}_6(S)$ are input uniform. Recall that $\{C, S\} \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle$, $\{C, S\} \vdash$
 $S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C : \langle \phi_2, \Lambda_2 \rangle$ and $\{C, B\} \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} B : \langle \phi_3, \Lambda_3 \rangle$. Then, observe that none of
 358 the following terms are typable:

$G_1 \equiv C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S + C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S$: this is because $\widehat{\phi}_1(C)$ cannot be disjoint from itself;

360 $G_2 \equiv C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S + S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C$: in this case we have that neither $\widehat{\phi}_1(C) \cup \widehat{\phi}_2(C) =$
 $\{CS!req, SC?done\}$ nor $\widehat{\phi}_1(S) \cup \widehat{\phi}_2(S) = \{CS?req, SC!done\}$ are output
 362 uniform;

$G_3 \equiv C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S + C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} B$: because $\{C, S\} \neq \{C, B\}$.

364 A more complex case is the following (continuing example 19):

$$\frac{\phi_1 = \Lambda_1 = \{CS!md, CS?md\}}{\{C, S\} \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle \quad \{C, S\} \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S; S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C : \langle \phi_2, \Lambda_3 \rangle}$$

$$\{C, S\} \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S + C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S; S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C : \langle \phi_1 \cup \phi_2, \Lambda_1 \cup \Lambda_3 \rangle$$

366 because C is the unique participant in $\{C, S\}$ such that $\widehat{\phi}_1(C)$ and $\widehat{\phi}_2(C)$ are
 output uniform, and the remaining S is such that $\widehat{\phi}_1(S)$ and $\widehat{\phi}_2(S)$ are input
 uniform, namely condition $\phi_1 \bowtie_{\{C, S\}} \phi_2$ is satisfied.

368 On the other hand the choreography $C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} B; B \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S + C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S; S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C$ is not
 typable because knowing from example 19 that

$$\{B, C, S\} \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} B; B \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S : \langle \phi_6, \Lambda_6 \rangle$$

we have that $\{B, C, S\} \neq \{C, S\}$, so that rule T-CH doesn't apply. \diamond

370 Our typing system is not complete. For instance, the g-choreography $A \xrightarrow{m} B \mid A \xrightarrow{m} C$
 372 is well-formed but it cannot be typed because the rule T-PAR cannot be applied
 since A occurs on both sides of the parallel. In fact, this is the only obstacle to
 374 attain completeness and could be removed by tracing in the types not only the
 minimal and maximal communications, but also the communications of threads.

376 **Lemma 21.** *If $\Pi \vdash G : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ is derivable then, for all $x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G \rrbracket)$ and*
 377 *$A \in \mathcal{P}$, either $\max(x \upharpoonright A)$ is empty or it is a singleton.*

378 *Proof.* By induction on the derivation of $\Pi \vdash G : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ and case analysis of the
 379 last typing rule applied observing that (i) rule T-PAR requires to partition the
 380 context in two disjoint sub-contexts and (ii) the thesis in the case of rule T-CH
 381 follows by the inductive hypothesis observing that configurations of $\llbracket G_1 \rrbracket$ and
 382 $\llbracket G_2 \rrbracket$ are in conflict, hence they cannot belong to the same maximal configuration
 of $\llbracket G \rrbracket$. \square

383 We remark that such a completeness result would be basically due to the
 384 strictness of the conditions of Definition 8. In fact, more general notions of
 well-branchedness would break the completeness theorem. For instance, we can
 385 weaken the conditions of Definition 8 as follows.

- 386 • The projections on the event structures of the two branches may either
 387 be disjoint inputs (as per the current determined choice condition) or be
 isomorphic
- 388 • there is a unique active (as currently required in Definition 8) and any
 389 other participant whose minimal actions are output have isomorphic pro-
 390 jections on the two branches.

391 With this change, the g-choreography $G = G_1 + G_2$ where $G_1 = A \xrightarrow{m} B; C \xrightarrow{x} B$
 392 and $G_2 = A \xrightarrow{n} B; C \xrightarrow{x} B$ would become well-formed. However, our system cannot
 393 type G since both A and C are active in the choice of G . Notice that G_1 violates
 394 the awareness condition of Definition 8, while it does not violate the more general
 395 conditions above since C behaves the same in G_1 and G_2 .

396 4. Refinement

397 We extend the grammar of Definition 5 with a new construct that we dub
 398 *refinable action*:

$$G ::= \dots \mid A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B} \quad \text{refinable action}$$

399 where $\bar{m} = m_1, \dots, m_n$ and $\bar{B} = B_1, \dots, B_n$ are non-empty tuples of the same
 400 length of messages and participants such that (i) \bar{m} and \bar{B} have the same
 401 length, and (ii) the participants in \bar{B} are pairwise distinct and all distinct from
 402 A . Call *refinable* a g-choreography generated by the so extended grammar;
 403 a g-choreography is *ground* or *non-refinable* if it is derivable only with the
 404 productions of the grammar in Definition 5.

405 **Definition 22** (Refines relation). *A ground g-choreography G refines $A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}$*
 406 *(with $\bar{m} = m_1, \dots, m_n$ and $\bar{B} = B_1, \dots, B_n$), if*

1. $\llbracket G \rrbracket = \mathcal{E} \neq \perp$;

- 410 2. $\text{sbj}(\min(\mathcal{E})) = \{A\}$, by which we say that A is the (unique) initiator of G ;
- 412 3. for all $x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\mathcal{E})$ and $1 \leq h \leq n$ there exists $C \in \mathcal{P}(G)$ such that $C B_h ? m_h \in \max(x \upharpoonright B_h)$.

We write $G \text{ ref } A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}$ when G refines $A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}$ and say that $A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}$ is ground-refinable if there exists some ground G such that $G \text{ ref } A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}$.

In words, G refines $A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}$ if G is meaningful, that is well-formed, with a unique participant A initiating the interaction by some output actions, and such that in all branches, namely maximal configurations x of $\llbracket G \rrbracket$, each B_h eventually inputs m_h .

Example 23. The following are examples of the refinement relation:

$$A \xrightarrow{m} B \text{ ref } A \xrightarrow{m} B, \quad A \xrightarrow{m} B + A \xrightarrow{n} B; A \xrightarrow{m} B \text{ ref } A \xrightarrow{m} B.$$

420 A more complex example, involving parallel composition, is:

$$A \xrightarrow{p} C; (A \xrightarrow{m} B \mid C \xrightarrow{n} D) \text{ ref } A \xrightarrow{m,n} B, D.$$

◇

Hereafter, let a context $G'[\cdot]$ be a ground g-choreography with a hole $[\cdot]$, namely a placeholder such that, if replaced by a ground G the resulting $G'[G]$ is a ground g-choreography. Our next step is to devise sufficient conditions for substituting the refinement action $A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}$ with some of its ground refinements G in a context of the shape $G'[A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}]$ while ensuring well-formedness of the resulting g-choreography $G'[G]$. In view of Section 3.2, an eligible tool is the typing system \mathcal{G} .

Observe that, except for axioms, the shape of a typing judgement $\Pi \vdash G : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ in the conclusion of each rule depends only on the contexts and types in its premises. Hence by adding postulates of the shape $\Pi \vdash A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B} : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ to the axioms in \mathcal{G} , we can derive judgements $\Pi' \vdash G'[A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}] : \langle \phi', \Lambda' \rangle$ ensuring the typability of any ground instance $G'[G]$ of the context $G'[\cdot]$ under the hypothesis that $\Pi \vdash G : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ is derivable. Combining this remark with Theorem 17, we get the following corollary.

Corollary 24. Suppose that, by postulating $\Pi \vdash A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B} : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$, the judgement $\Pi' \vdash G'[A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}] : \langle \phi', \Lambda' \rangle$ is derivable in system \mathcal{G} . Then for any ground G such that $\Pi \vdash G : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ is derivable, we have $\llbracket G'[G] \rrbracket \neq \perp$.

To put this result to use, we seek to extend the typing system in Figure 1 to refinable choreographies, and to this aim we need an axiom schema for deducing $\Pi \vdash A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B} : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ such that the following conditions are satisfied:

soundness: if $\Pi \vdash G : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ is derivable for some ground G , then G refines $A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}$;

inhabitation: there exists some ground G such that $\Pi \vdash G : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ is derivable.

444 **5. Soundness**

Towards establishing our soundness result (cf. Theorem 26 below) , we need
446 a lemma.

Lemma 25. *Let $\llbracket G \rrbracket \neq \epsilon$ be ground and well-formed. If $x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G \rrbracket)$ then*

- 448 1. $\emptyset \neq \min(x) \subseteq \mathcal{L}^!$ and $\emptyset \neq \max(x) \subseteq \mathcal{L}^?$;
2. $\mathbf{sbj}(x) = \mathcal{P}(G)$.

450 *Proof.* By induction over G .

BASE CASE $G \equiv A \xrightarrow{m} B$. Then, $\llbracket G \rrbracket = \{A B!m < A B?m\}$ and (1)-(2) are immediately verified.
452

CASE $G \equiv G_1 \mid G_2$. We have that $\llbracket G \rrbracket = \llbracket G_1 \rrbracket \otimes \llbracket G_2 \rrbracket$ by well-formedness. If
454 either of the $\llbracket G_i \rrbracket$ is ϵ then the thesis follows immediately by induction, since the other one has to be $\neq \epsilon$. Suppose that $\llbracket G_i \rrbracket \neq \epsilon$ for both $i = 1, 2$. By definition
456 of \otimes we have that for some non empty $x_i \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G_i \rrbracket)$ it is $x = x_1 \cup x_2$.
Part (1) immediately follows by the inductive hypothesis. Likewise, by induction
458 we have that $\mathbf{sbj}(x_i) = \mathcal{P}(G_i)$ for $i \in \{1, 2\}$. Observe that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{sbj}(x) &= \{\mathbf{sbj}(e) \mid \mathbf{sbj}(e) \in x\} && \text{by extending element-wise the def of } \mathbf{sbj}(_) \text{ to sets} \\ &= \mathbf{sbj}(x_1 \cup x_2) && \text{since } x = x_1 \cup x_2 \\ &= \{\mathbf{sbj}(e) \mid \mathbf{sbj}(e) \in x_1 \cup x_2\} \\ &= \{\mathbf{sbj}(e) \mid \mathbf{sbj}(e) \in x_1\} \cup \{\mathbf{sbj}(e) \mid \mathbf{sbj}(e) \in x_2\} \\ &= \mathbf{sbj}(x_1) \cup \mathbf{sbj}(x_2) \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mathbf{sbj}(x) = \mathbf{sbj}(x_1) \cup \mathbf{sbj}(x_2) = \mathcal{P}(G_1) \cup \mathcal{P}(G_2) = \mathcal{P}(G)$ where the last equality
460 holds by definition of $\mathcal{P}(_)$.

CASE $G \equiv G_1 ; G_2$. By definition of $\llbracket G \rrbracket = \mathbf{seq}(\llbracket G_1 \rrbracket, \llbracket G_2 \rrbracket)$, any $x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G \rrbracket)$
462 either $x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G_1 \rrbracket)$, or $x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G_2 \rrbracket)$ or else there exist $x_1 \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G_1 \rrbracket)$ and
 $x_2 \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G_2 \rrbracket)$ with $x = x_1 \cup x_2$ and $\min(x) = \min(x_1)$, $\max(x) = \max(x_2)$.
464 Now (1) follows by induction. To prove part (2) we observe that $x = x_1 \cup x_2$
with $x_1 \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G_1 \rrbracket)$ and $x_2 \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G_2 \rrbracket)$; hence $\mathbf{sbj}(x) = \mathbf{sbj}(x_1) \cup \mathbf{sbj}(x_2) =$
466 $\mathcal{P}(G_1) \cup \mathcal{P}(G_2) = \mathcal{P}(G)$ where the last two equalities hold by induction and by
definition of $\mathcal{P}(_)$ respectively.

468 CASE $G \equiv G_1 + G_2$. By well-branchedness $\mathcal{P}(G_1) = \mathcal{P}(G_2) = \mathcal{P}(G)$; moreover,
here exists a unique active $A \in \mathcal{P}(G)$ in $\llbracket G \rrbracket = \llbracket G_1 \rrbracket + \llbracket G_2 \rrbracket$ that is the subject of
470 all events in $\min(x)$ for any $x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G \rrbracket)$. This also implies that $\llbracket G \rrbracket \neq \epsilon$, so
that at least one of the two $\llbracket G_i \rrbracket$ is such. By induction we have immediately (1).
472 To prove (2) we observe that $\mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G \rrbracket) = \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G_1 \rrbracket) \cup \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G_2 \rrbracket)$ by definition
of $\llbracket G_1 \rrbracket + \llbracket G_2 \rrbracket$. Hence, $x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G_1 \rrbracket)$ or $x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G_2 \rrbracket)$; the thesis follows by
474 induction. \square

We say that B eventually receives m in Λ when $\emptyset \neq \widehat{\Lambda}(B) \subseteq \{CB?m \mid C \in \text{sbj}(\Lambda) \setminus \{B\}\}$.

Theorem 26 (Soundness). *Let $A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}$ be a refinable action with $\bar{m} = m_1, \dots, m_n$ and $\bar{B} = B_1, \dots, B_n$. If $\Pi \subseteq \mathcal{P}$ and $\phi, \Lambda \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ are such that*

1. $\text{sbj}(\phi) = \text{sbj}(\Lambda) = \Pi$,
2. $\text{sbj}(\phi \cap \mathcal{L}^\dagger) = \{A\}$, and
3. B_i eventually receives m_i in Λ for all $1 \leq i \leq n$

then $\Pi \vdash G : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ implies $G \text{ ref } A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}$.

Proof. By Theorem 17, we know that $\Pi \vdash G : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ implies $\llbracket G \rrbracket \neq \perp$; also, the hypotheses imply that none among Π , ϕ and Λ is empty. Consequently, $\llbracket G \rrbracket \neq \epsilon$. Recall that, by the same theorem, $\widehat{\phi}(C) = \min(\llbracket G \rrbracket \upharpoonright C)$ and $\widehat{\Lambda}(C) = \max(\llbracket G \rrbracket \upharpoonright C)$ for all $C \in \Pi = \mathcal{P}(G)$.

Let $x \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G \rrbracket)$. We have $\emptyset \neq \min(x) \subseteq \phi \cap \mathcal{L}^\dagger$ by the above and by Lemma 25.1, hence $\text{sbj}(\phi \cap \mathcal{L}^\dagger) = \{A\}$ implies $\text{sbj}(\min(x)) = \{A\}$, and therefore A is the initiator of G .

By hypothesis 3, each $B_h \in \bar{B}$ eventually receives m_h in Λ and, by Theorem 17, $\widehat{\Lambda}(B_h) = \max(\llbracket G \rrbracket \upharpoonright B_h)$. Hence $\max(\llbracket G \rrbracket \upharpoonright B_h) \subseteq \{CB_h?m_h \mid C \in \Pi \setminus \{B_h\}\}$. Therefore there exists $y \in \mathcal{C}_{\max}(\llbracket G \rrbracket)$ such that $CB_h?m_h \in y \cap \Lambda$ for some $C \in \Pi$; by Lemma 25.2, $\text{sbj}(x) = \text{sbj}(y)$, hence $B_h \in \text{sbj}(x)$ and so $\widehat{x}(B_h) \neq \emptyset$. This and the typability of G imply that $\widehat{x}(B_h)$ is a singleton by Lemma 21: from this and the fact that $\max(x \upharpoonright B_h) \subseteq \Lambda$ it follows that $\max(x \upharpoonright B_h) \subseteq \widehat{\Lambda}(B_h) \subseteq \{CB_h?m_h \mid C \in \Pi \setminus \{B_h\}\}$. \square

6. Inhabitation

Theorem 26 provides sufficient conditions on a typing context Π, ϕ, Λ such that any ground G that is typable in such a context is a refinement of $A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}$, so that the soundness condition is satisfied. We now turn our attention on the (complementary) problem of *inhabitation*, namely the problem of establishing if the extension of a given type is empty or not. If one interprets types as specifications, inhabitation corresponds to establish that the specification is not inconsistent. It is easy to see that given any refinable action there is a typing context satisfying the conditions of Theorem 26. Indeed, for $A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}$ with $\bar{m} = m_1 \dots m_n$ and $\bar{B} = B_1, \dots, B_n$ it suffices to take e.g., the context

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_0 &= \{A, B_1, \dots, B_n\} \\ \phi_0 &= \{AB_1!m_1, AB_1?m_1, AB_2?m_2, \dots, AB_n?m_n\} \\ \Lambda_0 &= \{AB_n!m_n, AB_1?m_1, AB_2?m_2, \dots, AB_n?m_n\} \end{aligned}$$

This context is inhabited by ground g-choreographies (e.g., the one in which A successively sends the corresponding message to each B_i), but it is overly restrictive because it forbids, e.g., other participants to take place in the refinement.

510 Moreover, a context Π, ϕ, Λ that satisfy the conditions in Theorem 26 does
 not ensure the existence of a ground G that is typable in such a context, as
 512 shown in the next example.

Example 27. *The context Π, ϕ, Λ with*

$$\Pi = \{A, B, C, D\}, \quad \text{and} \quad \phi = \Lambda = \{AB!m, AB?m, DC?m, CD?m\}$$

*satisfies the hypothesis of Theorem 26. Nonetheless, there does not exist a
 ground G such that $\Pi \vdash G : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$, because the minimal events in ϕ account
 for a deadlocked interaction between C and D since each of them start by wait-
 ing a message from the other. \diamond*

514 In the remaining parts of this section we give conditions on type judgements
 $\Pi \vdash A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B} : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ for them to be inhabited by ground refinements; namely,
 516 we identify conditions on the typing context Π, ϕ, Λ to ensure that there exists
 a ground g-choreography G such that $\Pi \vdash G : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$. We do this in two steps.
 518 Firstly, we distil conditions about the minimal events ϕ that ensure the exist-
 ence of a ground g-choreography whose minimal events are exactly those in ϕ .
 520 Similarly, we identify conditions on Λ that guarantee the existence of a ground
 g-choreography whose maximal events are exactly those in Λ . Consequently,
 522 the existence of a ground g-choreography characterised by well-formed typing
 context Π, ϕ and Λ is straightforwardly obtained by sequential composition.

524 6.1. Well-formed sets of minimal events

Since $A \xrightarrow{\bar{m}} \bar{B}$ is meant to be substituted by a ground g-choreography whose
 526 initiator is A , we require every output in ϕ to be performed by A , i.e., $\text{sbj}(\phi \cap \mathcal{L}!) =$
 $\{A\}$. In this way, every participant but A starts by receiving a message. Failing
 528 this condition would imply that at least one participant different from A can
 autonomously start sending messages. This condition is however insufficient to
 530 ensure the existence of a ground g-choreography whose minimal events match
 those of the a set. For instance, it is impossible to provide a ground well-formed
 532 g-choreography in the following cases:

- 534 1. $\phi_1 = \{AB!m, AB?n\}$ because the output event of A does not match the
 minimal event from B , which should be the dual of $AB!m$;
- 536 2. $\phi_2 = \{AB!m, AB?m, CD?n\}$ because the participant D starts by receiving
 a message from C , which does not have a minimal event in ϕ_2 ;
- 538 3. $\phi_3 = \{AB!m, AB?m, CD?n, DC?n\}$ because it is not enough to require
 that every participant has a minimal event; in fact, C and D would be
 deadlocked reciprocally waiting for a message;
- 540 4. $\phi_4 = \{AB!m, AB?m, BC?m, AB!n, AB?n\}$ because participant C would
 take part only on one of the two branches that A chooses by sending
 542 either message m or n to B .

544 All the cases above have in common the fact that something is wrong in the
causality order induced by the output/input relation w.r.t. all the participants.

546 Definition 28 below formalises the relation \triangleleft to rule out such cases. In-
tuitively, $\Pi \triangleleft L$ states that the participants in $\Pi \subseteq \mathcal{P}$ *orderly initiate* a set of
548 actions $L \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ when the actions in L causally depend on actions to be performed
by participants in Π . Hence, we expect $\emptyset \triangleleft L$ to hold when for every input
550 action $l \in L$ there is a sequence of actions starting from an output $l' \in L$ such
that each two consecutive elements of the sequence share a participant; notice
552 that l' is not necessarily the dual of l .

We formalise this notion as follows.

554 **Definition 28** (Orderly initiation). *Let $\Pi \triangleleft L$ be the least relation satisfying the
following rules*

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\Pi \triangleleft \emptyset} \triangleleft\text{-END} \qquad \frac{A, B \triangleleft L}{\emptyset \triangleleft AB!m, AB?m, L} \triangleleft\text{-ACTIVE} \\
\frac{A, B, \Pi \triangleleft L}{A, \Pi \triangleleft AB?m, L} \triangleleft\text{-PASSIVE} \qquad \frac{\Pi \triangleleft L_1 \quad \Pi \triangleleft L_2 \quad \text{subj}(L_1) = \text{subj}(L_2) \neq \emptyset \quad \#\Pi \neq 1}{\Pi \triangleleft L_1, L_2} \triangleleft\text{-COMP}
\end{array}$$

556 where $_, _$ reads as disjoint union of singletons or sets and $\# _$ denotes the cardi-
nality of a set.

Let us comment on the rules in Definition 28. Rule ($\triangleleft\text{-END}$) is self-explanatory.
558 Rule ($\triangleleft\text{-ACTIVE}$) states that a set is “fully” orderly initiated when it contains two
dual actions $AB!m$ and $AB?m$ accounting for the first interaction between par-
560 ticipants A and B capable of triggering the remaining actions in the set. Rule
($\triangleleft\text{-PASSIVE}$) allows an input $AB?m$ to be orderly initiated if the sender A can or-
562 derly initiate the remaining actions possibly together with the receiver B (which
can trigger other input actions by sending a message after executing $AB?m$).
564 Note that the rules ($\triangleleft\text{-ACTIVE}$) and ($\triangleleft\text{-PASSIVE}$) ensure a linear usage of participants,
namely a participant orderly initiates one action only. Consequently, these rules
566 cannot account for sets describing choices, where participants should orderly ini-
tiate alternative actions. Rule ($\triangleleft\text{-COMP}$) takes care of that. A set of participants
568 Π can orderly initiate two disjoint sets of actions provided that Π can orderly
initiate both of them; the third premise of rule ($\triangleleft\text{-COMP}$) is a necessary condition
570 of well-branchedness while its last premise is included for technical convenience
without compromising the judgements because our main results concern deriva-
572 tions of the form $\emptyset \triangleleft L$.

Example 29. Consider the set of actions $L = \{AB!m, AB?m, BC?m, BC?n\}$.
574 The proof that $\emptyset \triangleleft L$ holds is as follows:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{A, B, C \triangleleft \emptyset} \triangleleft\text{-END} \qquad \frac{}{A, B, C \triangleleft \emptyset} \triangleleft\text{-END} \\
\frac{}{A, B \triangleleft \{BC?m\}} \triangleleft\text{-PASSIVE} \qquad \frac{}{A, B \triangleleft \{BC?n\}} \triangleleft\text{-PASSIVE} \\
\frac{}{A, B \triangleleft \{BC?m, BC?n\}} \triangleleft\text{-COMP} \\
\frac{}{\emptyset \triangleleft \{AB!m, AB?m, BC?m, BC?n\}} \triangleleft\text{-ACTIVE}
\end{array}$$

where $\text{subj}(\{BC?m\}) = \{C\} = \text{subj}(\{BC?n\}) \neq \emptyset$ and $\#\{A, B\} \neq 1$ are the other premises of rule $\triangleleft\text{-COMP}$. \diamond

We now state properties about the orderly initiation relation, which are instrumental for the proof of the main result in this section. The first one highlights that actions in L are not performed by participants in Π if $\Pi \triangleleft L$ holds; intuitively, the set L lacks minimal events for participants in Π .

Lemma 30. *If $\Pi \triangleleft L$ then $\text{subj}(L) \cap \Pi = \emptyset$.*

Proof. By straightforward induction on the derivation of $\Pi \triangleleft L$. \square

The following lemma states that a set of actions L that depends on a non-empty set of participants Π consists only of input actions. Moreover, if L is not empty, then there is (at least) an input action of a message that should be sent by a participant in Π . Intuitively, the occurrence of the actions in L depends on the occurrence of an action performed by some participant in Π .

Lemma 31. *If $\Pi \triangleleft L$ and $\Pi \neq \emptyset$ then (i) $L \subseteq \mathcal{L}^?$ and (ii) if $L \neq \emptyset$ then there exists $A \in \Pi$ such that $AB?m \in L$.*

Proof. By induction on the derivation of $\Pi \triangleleft L$. Case ($\triangleleft\text{-END}$) straightforwardly holds since $L = \emptyset$. Case ($\triangleleft\text{-ACTIVE}$) implies $\Pi = \emptyset$, which contradicts the assumption $\Pi \neq \emptyset$. Cases ($\triangleleft\text{-PASSIVE}$) and ($\triangleleft\text{-COMP}$) follow by inductive hypothesis and the simple inspection of the conclusions of the rules. \square

The following lemma states that a set of actions that causally depend on an empty set of participants contains at least one output action, i.e., the interaction is started by an output present in the set. We write $\triangleleft L$ when $L \neq \emptyset$ and $\emptyset \triangleleft L$.

Lemma 32. *If $\triangleleft L$ then $L \cap \mathcal{L}^! \neq \emptyset$.*

Proof. We show by induction on the derivation of $\emptyset \triangleleft L$ that $L \neq \emptyset$ implies $L \cap \mathcal{L}^! \neq \emptyset$.

CASE ($\triangleleft\text{-END}$). Hence, $L = \emptyset$ and the implication trivially holds.

CASE ($\triangleleft\text{-ACTIVE}$). Then, there exists L' such that $L = AB!m, AB?m, L'$. Hence, $L \cap \mathcal{L}^! \neq \emptyset$ holds because $AB!m \in \mathcal{L}^!$.

CASE ($\triangleleft\text{-PASSIVE}$). It is not possible, because $A, \Pi \neq \emptyset$.

CASE ($\triangleleft\text{-COMP}$). Then, $L = L_1, L_2$ and $\text{subj}(L_1) = \text{subj}(L_2) \neq \emptyset$. For $i = 1, 2$, we have $L_i \neq \emptyset$ implies $L_i \cap \mathcal{L}^! \neq \emptyset$ by inductive hypothesis on $\emptyset \triangleleft L_i$. Since

604 $\text{sbj}(L_i) \neq \emptyset$, we have that $L_i \neq \emptyset$; and hence $L_i \cap \mathcal{L}^! \neq \emptyset$ holds. Therefore,
 605 $L \cap \mathcal{L}^! \neq \emptyset$ holds.

606 The proof is completed by noting that $\triangleleft L$ stands for $L \neq \emptyset$ and $\emptyset \triangleleft L$. \square

A set of actions L satisfying $\triangleleft L$ and having at most one active participant
 608 (namely $L \cap \mathcal{L}^!$ is empty or a singleton) corresponds to a (well-branched) g-
 choreography whose initial interactions yield the actions in L . The next steps
 610 in this section are about the construction of a ground choreography $\langle L \rangle_\Pi$ which
 exists and is well formed if $\Pi \triangleleft L$, see Theorem 36; moreover, there are $\phi, \Lambda \subseteq \mathcal{L}$
 612 such that $\text{sbj}(\phi) \subseteq \Pi$ and $\text{sbj}(L) \cup \text{sbj}(\phi) \vdash \langle L \rangle_\Pi : \langle L \cup \phi, \Lambda \rangle$, see Lemma 37.
 When $\Pi = \emptyset$ this implies that $\text{sbj}(L) \vdash \langle L \rangle_\emptyset : \langle L, \Lambda \rangle$ for some Λ , see Corol-
 614 lary 38.

The following operation is instrumental to exhibit such correspondence. Let
 616 $A \xrightarrow{m} \Pi; G$ be a g-choreography where participant $A \in \mathcal{P}$ sends message $m \in \mathcal{M}$
 to each participant in Π different from A and then continues as G ; formally:

$$A \xrightarrow{m} \Pi; G = \begin{cases} G & \text{if } \Pi \subseteq \{A\} \\ A \xrightarrow{m} B; (A \xrightarrow{m} \Pi'; G) & \text{if } \Pi = B, \Pi' \text{ and } A \neq B \end{cases}$$

618 Notice that $A \xrightarrow{m} \Pi; G$ non-deterministically fixes the order in which message m is
 delivered to the participants in $\Pi \setminus A$. Consequently, it defines a relation instead
 620 of a function. Interestingly, all possible choices are characterised by the same
 sets of minimal and maximal events. For this reason, the particular choice is
 622 immaterial for the encoding $\langle L \rangle_\Pi$ defined below.

$$\langle L \rangle_\Pi = \begin{cases} \mathbf{0} & \text{if } L = \emptyset \\ A \xrightarrow{m} B; \langle L' \rangle_{A,B} & \text{if } \triangleleft L \text{ and } L = AB!m, AB?m, L' \\ A \xrightarrow{m} B; \langle L' \rangle_{B,\Pi} & \text{if } A \in \Pi \text{ and } L = AB?m, L' \text{ and } B, \Pi \triangleleft L' \\ \langle L_1 \rangle_\Pi + \langle L_2 \rangle_\Pi & \text{if } \Pi = \emptyset \text{ and } L = L_1, L_2 \text{ and } L_1 \neq \emptyset \text{ and } L_2 \neq \emptyset \\ & \text{and } \triangleleft L_1 \text{ and } \text{causal} L_2 \\ G + G' & \text{if } A \in \Pi \text{ and } L = L_1, L_2 \text{ and } L_1 \neq \emptyset \text{ and } L_2 \neq \emptyset \text{ and} \\ & \Pi \triangleleft L_1 \text{ and } \Pi \triangleleft L_2 \text{ and } G = A \xrightarrow{\text{left}} \Pi; \langle L_1 \rangle_\Pi \text{ and} \\ & G' = A \xrightarrow{\text{right}} \Pi; \langle L_2 \rangle_\Pi \end{cases}$$

under the assumption that none of the actions in L uses messages $\text{left} \neq \text{right}$.
 624 We write $\langle L \rangle$ instead of $\langle L \rangle_\emptyset$. Note that $\langle _ \rangle__$ is a partial, non-deterministic
 operation.

626 **Example 33.** Let us illustrate the encoding $\langle L \rangle_\emptyset$ for the set $L = \{AB!m, AB?m, BC?m, BC?n\}$
 of Example 29. Recall that $\emptyset \triangleleft L$ holds. We observe that the fourth case in the
 628 definition of $\langle _ \rangle__$ is not applicable because L should be split in L_1 and L_2 such that
 $\triangleleft L_1$ and $\triangleleft L_2$, each of them containing an output action because of Lemma 31.
 630 In fact, the only applicable case is the second one, namely

$$\langle L \rangle_\emptyset = A \xrightarrow{m} B; \langle BC?m, BC?n \rangle_{\{A,B\}} \quad (11)$$

632 Note that both $A, B \triangleleft \{BC?m\}$ and $A, B \triangleleft \{BC?n\}$ hold and the only possible
applicable case is the last one. We can proceed by non-deterministically selecting
either A or B ; choosing A , we have

$$\langle BC?m, BC?n \rangle_{\{A,B\}} = A \xrightarrow{\text{left}} \{A, B\}; \langle BC?m \rangle_{\{A,B\}} + A \xrightarrow{\text{right}} \{A, B\}; \langle BC?n \rangle_{\{A,B\}} \quad (12)$$

634 We then get

$$\langle BC?m, BC?n \rangle_{\{A,B\}} = A \xrightarrow{\text{left}} B; \langle BC?m \rangle_{\{A,B\}} + A \xrightarrow{\text{right}} B; \langle BC?n \rangle_{\{A,B\}}$$

since, by definition of $A \xrightarrow{m} \Pi; G$,

$$\begin{aligned} A \xrightarrow{\text{left}} \{A, B\}; \langle BC?m \rangle_{\{A,B\}} &= A \xrightarrow{\text{left}} B; \langle BC?m \rangle_{\{A,B\}} \\ A \xrightarrow{\text{right}} \{A, B\}; \langle BC?n \rangle_{\{A,B\}} &= A \xrightarrow{\text{right}} B; \langle BC?n \rangle_{\{A,B\}} \end{aligned}$$

636 Using the second and the first cases of the definition of $(\lfloor _ \rfloor)_-$, we obtain
 $\langle BC?m \rangle_{\{A,B\}} = B \xrightarrow{m} C; \mathbf{0}$ and $\langle BC?n \rangle_{\{A,B\}} = B \xrightarrow{n} C; \mathbf{0}$. Consequently,

$$\langle BC?m, BC?n \rangle_{\{A,B\}} = A \xrightarrow{\text{left}} B; B \xrightarrow{n} C; \mathbf{0} + A \xrightarrow{\text{right}} B; B \xrightarrow{m} C; \mathbf{0} \quad (13)$$

638 Finally

$$\langle L \rangle_{\emptyset} = A \xrightarrow{m} B; (A \xrightarrow{\text{left}} B; B \xrightarrow{m} C; \mathbf{0} + A \xrightarrow{\text{right}} B; B \xrightarrow{n} C; \mathbf{0})$$

follows from equalities (12) and (13). \diamond

Note that the result of the encoding depends on non-deterministic choices,
640 as shown in the next example.

Example 34. Let consider $\langle BC?m, BC?n \rangle_{\{A,B\}}$ from Example 33 and partition
642 the set $\{BC?m, BC?n\}$ into $L_1 = \{BC?n\}$ and $L_2 = \{BC?m\}$. We obtain the
following encoding:

$$\langle L \rangle_{\emptyset} = A \xrightarrow{m} B; (A \xrightarrow{\text{left}} B; B \xrightarrow{n} C; \mathbf{0} + A \xrightarrow{\text{right}} B; B \xrightarrow{m} C; \mathbf{0})$$

644 Analogously, if in Example 33 instead of choosing A we had selected B for
communicating the choice, then

$$\langle L \rangle_{\emptyset} = A \xrightarrow{m} B; (B \xrightarrow{\text{left}} A; B \xrightarrow{n} C; \mathbf{0} + B \xrightarrow{\text{right}} A; B \xrightarrow{m} C; \mathbf{0})$$

would have been the resulting g -choreography. \diamond

646 Remarkably, all the possible choices for $\langle L \rangle_{\emptyset}$ preserve the minimal actions for
the subjects of the actions in L , as formally stated by the following proposition.

648 **Proposition 35.** If $\Pi \triangleleft L$ then $\min(\llbracket \langle L \rangle_{\Pi} \rrbracket \uparrow X) = \widehat{L}(X)$ for all $X \in \text{subj}(L)$.

Proof. By induction on the derivation of $\Pi \triangleleft L$.

650 **BASE CASE** (\triangleleft -END). We have $L = \emptyset$ and $\langle L \rangle_{\Pi} = \mathbf{0}$ by construction. The thesis follows vacuously since $\text{sbj}(L) = \emptyset$.

652 **CASE** (\triangleleft -ACTIVE). If the derivation of $\Pi \triangleleft L$ ends with an instance of (\triangleleft -ACTIVE) then

$$L = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B}! \mathbf{m}, \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} ? \mathbf{m}, L' \quad \Pi = \emptyset \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B} \triangleleft L'.$$

654 Therefore, by construction $\langle L \rangle_{\Pi} = \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{\mathbf{m}} \mathbf{B}; \langle L' \rangle_{\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}}$. Note that, by Lemma 30, $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B} \notin \text{sbj}(L')$ and therefore the thesis follows by induction hypothesis on any $\mathbf{X} \in \text{sbj}(L')$ while for \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} it suffices to observe that $\min(\langle \langle L \rangle_{\Pi} \rangle \uparrow \mathbf{A}) = \{\mathbf{A} \mathbf{B}! \mathbf{m}\} = \widehat{L}(\mathbf{A})$ and $\min(\langle \langle L \rangle_{\Pi} \rangle \uparrow \mathbf{B}) = \{\mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} ? \mathbf{m}\} = \widehat{L}(\mathbf{B})$.

658 **CASE** (\triangleleft -PASSIVE). If the derivation of $\Pi \triangleleft L$ ends with an instance of (\triangleleft -PASSIVE) then

$$L = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} ? \mathbf{m}, L' \quad \Pi = \mathbf{A}, \Pi' \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{B}, \Pi \triangleleft L'.$$

660 By construction $\langle L \rangle_{\Pi} = \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{\mathbf{m}} \mathbf{B}; \langle L' \rangle_{\mathbf{B}, \Pi}$ and, by Lemma 30, $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B} \notin \text{sbj}(L')$. Hence $\min(\langle \langle L \rangle_{\Pi} \rangle \uparrow \mathbf{A}) = \{\mathbf{A} \mathbf{B}! \mathbf{m}\} = \widehat{L}(\mathbf{A})$, $\min(\langle \langle L \rangle_{\Pi} \rangle \uparrow \mathbf{B}) = \{\mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} ? \mathbf{m}\} = \widehat{L}(\mathbf{B})$, and for all $\mathbf{X} \in \text{sbj}(L')$ $\min(\langle \langle L \rangle_{\Pi} \rangle \uparrow \mathbf{X}) = \widehat{L}(\mathbf{X})$ by inductive hypothesis.

CASE (\triangleleft -COMP). If the derivation of $\Pi \triangleleft L$ ends with an instance of (\triangleleft -COMP) then

$$L = L_1, L_2 \quad \Pi \triangleleft L_1 \quad \Pi \triangleleft L_2 \quad \text{sbj}(L_1) = \text{sbj}(L_2) \neq \emptyset \quad \text{and} \quad \sharp \Pi \neq 1$$

664 We consider the following two cases.

CASE $\Pi = \emptyset$. By construction $\langle L \rangle_{\Pi} = \langle L_1 \rangle_{\Pi} + \langle L_2 \rangle_{\Pi}$. By inductive hypothesis, for $i = 1, 2$, $\min(\langle \langle L_i \rangle_{\Pi} \rangle \uparrow \mathbf{X}) = \widehat{L}_i(\mathbf{X})$ for all $\mathbf{X} \in \text{sbj}(L_i)$. Then, $\min(\langle \langle L \rangle_{\Pi} \rangle \uparrow \mathbf{X}) = \min(\langle \langle L_1 \rangle_{\Pi} \rangle \uparrow \mathbf{X}) \cup \min(\langle \langle L_2 \rangle_{\Pi} \rangle \uparrow \mathbf{X}) = \widehat{L}_1(\mathbf{X}) \cup \widehat{L}_2(\mathbf{X}) = \widehat{L}(\mathbf{X})$.

668 CASE $\sharp \Pi \geq 2$. By construction, $\langle L \rangle_{\Pi} = \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{G}'$ where, for an $\mathbf{A} \in \Pi$,

$$\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{\text{left}} \Pi; \langle L_1 \rangle_{\Pi} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{G}' = \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{\text{right}} \Pi; \langle L_2 \rangle_{\Pi}$$

670 By induction, for $i \in \{1, 2\}$ and each $\mathbf{X} \in \text{sbj}(L_i)$ we have $\min(\langle \langle L_i \rangle_{\Pi} \rangle \uparrow \mathbf{X}) = \widehat{L}_i(\mathbf{X})$. Note that $\Pi \triangleleft L_i$ implies $\text{sbj}(L_i) \cap \Pi = \emptyset$ by Lemma 30. Also, $L_1 \subseteq \min(\langle \langle \mathbf{G} \rangle \rangle)$ and $L_2 \subseteq \min(\langle \langle \mathbf{G}' \rangle \rangle)$ hold because $\text{sbj}(\max(\langle \langle \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{\text{left}} \Pi; \mathbf{0} \rangle \rangle)) = \text{sbj}(\max(\langle \langle \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{\text{right}} \Pi; \mathbf{0} \rangle \rangle)) = \Pi$. Then, the thesis follows by observing that, for $\mathbf{X} \in \text{sbj}(L)$, $\min(\langle \langle L \rangle_{\Pi} \rangle \uparrow \mathbf{X}) = \min(\langle \langle \mathbf{G} \rangle \rangle \uparrow \mathbf{X}) \cup \min(\langle \langle \mathbf{G}' \rangle \rangle \uparrow \mathbf{X}) = \widehat{L}_1(\mathbf{X}) \cup \widehat{L}_2(\mathbf{X}) = \widehat{L}(\mathbf{X})$. \square

676 The definition of $\langle _ \rangle_{_}$ may generate ill-formed g-choreographies, e.g., if we consider $L = \{\mathbf{A} \mathbf{B}! \mathbf{m}, \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} ? \mathbf{m}, \mathbf{C} \mathbf{D}! \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{C} \mathbf{D} ? \mathbf{n}\}$ then $\langle L \rangle_{\emptyset} = \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{\mathbf{m}} \mathbf{B}; \mathbf{0} + \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\mathbf{n}} \mathbf{D}; \mathbf{0}$. However, this may happen when encoding sets that do not correspond to an orderly initiation (as in the previous example) or include output actions with different senders, as formally stated below.

680 **Theorem 36.** *If $\Pi \triangleleft L$ and $\#sbj(L \cap \mathcal{L}^!) \leq 1$ then $\langle L \rangle_\Pi$ is defined and it is well-formed.*

682 *Proof.* It suffices to prove the well-branchedness conditions since $\langle L \rangle_\Pi$ does not contain parallel g-choreographies. We proceed by induction on the derivation of $\Pi \triangleleft L$.
684

BASE CASE (\triangleleft -END). The thesis easily follows since $L = \emptyset$, hence $\langle L \rangle_\Pi = \mathbf{0}$.

686 CASE (\triangleleft -ACTIVE). We have

$$L = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} ! \mathbf{m}, \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} ? \mathbf{m}, L' \quad \Pi = \emptyset \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B} \triangleleft L'. \quad \text{Then,}$$

The first case in the definition of $\langle _ \rangle_\Pi$ is not applicable because $L \neq \emptyset$; moreover, the conditions of the third and fifth cases are not satisfied because $\Pi = \emptyset$. The fourth rule is also precluded: assume $L = L_1, L_2$ such that L_1 and L_2 are non-empty and $\triangleleft L_1$ and $\triangleleft L_2$. By Lemma Lemma 32, $L_1 \cap \mathcal{L}^! \neq \emptyset$ and $L_2 \cap \mathcal{L}^! \neq \emptyset$. Hence, $\#(L \cap \mathcal{L}^!) \geq 2$. However, $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B} \triangleleft L'$ implies $L' \subseteq \mathcal{L}^?$ by Lemma 31; and hence $\#(L \cap \mathcal{L}^!) = 1$, which is in contradiction with $\#(L \cap \mathcal{L}^!) \geq 2$. Therefore, the only applicable case in the definition of $\langle _ \rangle_\Pi$ when $L \neq \emptyset$ and $\Pi = \emptyset$ is the second one. Hence, $\langle L \rangle_\Pi = \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{\mathbf{m}} \mathbf{B}; \langle L' \rangle_{\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}}$. And, since $L' \cap \mathcal{L}^! \subseteq L \cap \mathcal{L}^!$ we can apply the inductive hypothesis on $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B} \triangleleft L'$ and obtain that $\langle L' \rangle_{\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}}$ is well-branched.
696

CASE (\triangleleft -PASSIVE). In this case

$$L = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} ? \mathbf{m}, L' \quad \Pi = \mathbf{A}, \Pi' \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \Pi' \triangleleft L'$$

698 We can apply the third case of the definition of $\langle _ \rangle_\Pi$ because $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \Pi' \triangleleft L'$ implies $\mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} ! \mathbf{m} \notin L'$ (by Lemma 30); as in the previous case the inductive hypothesis implies the well-branchedness of $\langle L \rangle_\Pi$.
700

CASE (\triangleleft -COMP). We have $\# \Pi \neq 1$ and $L = L_1, L_2$ such that

$$\Pi \triangleleft L_1 \quad \Pi \triangleleft L_2 \quad \text{and} \quad sbj(L_1) = sbj(L_2) \neq \emptyset$$

702 note that the last inequality implies that L, L_1 , and L_2 are non-empty. Hence, for $i \in \{1, 2\}$, we have

- 704 (a) $L_i \cap \mathcal{L}^! \neq \emptyset$
(b) $\langle L_i \rangle_\Pi$ is well-branched

706 where (a) holds by Lemma 32, and (b) holds by inductive hypothesis: note that $L_i \subseteq L$ and the hypothesis $\#sbj(L \cap \mathcal{L}^!) \leq 1$ implies $\#sbj(L_i \cap \mathcal{L}^!) \leq 1$. Moreover, $\#sbj(L_i \cap \mathcal{L}^!) = 1$ because (a) holds. We distinguish two cases.
708

CASE $\Pi = \emptyset$. Then $\langle L \rangle_\Pi = \langle L_1 \rangle_\Pi + \langle L_2 \rangle_\Pi$ by definition. Let $\mathcal{E}_1 = \llbracket \langle L_1 \rangle_\Pi \rrbracket$ and $\mathcal{E}_2 = \llbracket \langle L_2 \rangle_\Pi \rrbracket$. Then $wf(\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2)$ because (i) the determinacy condition of
710

Definition 8 holds because the events in \mathcal{E}_1 and those in \mathcal{E}_2 are in conflict and
 712 (by Proposition 35) the labels of their minimal events are those in L_1 and L_2
 respectively; and (ii) the awareness condition of Definition 8 holds since the
 714 participants occurring in the events of \mathcal{E} are those in $\text{subj}(L)$.

CASE $\#\Pi \geq 2$. The thesis easily follows by observing that there is a unique active
 716 participant, say A , in $\langle L \rangle_\Pi$ which is (arbitrarily) chosen among the participants
 in Π to send messages **left** or **right** to any other participant of Π . Therefore,
 718 each $B \in \Pi \setminus \{A\}$ is passive and receives **left** on one branch and **right** on the
 other branch. Finally, all $X \in \text{subj}(L_i)$ for $i \in \{1, 2\}$, the thesis follows by
 720 Proposition 35 and Lemma 31 which imply that the minimal actions in L with
 subject X causally depend on events in $\llbracket \langle L \rangle_\Pi \rrbracket$. \square

The following lemma shows that $\langle L \rangle_\Pi$ is well-typed if $\Pi \triangleleft L$ holds and L
 contains output actions from at most one sender. For the case in which $\triangleleft L$,
 the result implies that there exists a set of labels $\Lambda \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ for maximal elements
 such that $\text{subj}(L) \vdash \langle L \rangle : \langle L, \Lambda \rangle$ is derivable, i.e., $\langle L \rangle$ has the set of participants
 $\text{subj}(L)$ and its minimal and maximal events are labelled respectively by L and
 Λ . However, its formalisation is more involved to account for judgements $L \triangleleft \Pi$
 where Π is not empty. As illustrated in Example 33, $\langle \text{BC?m} \rangle_{\{A,B\}} = \text{B}^m \text{C}; \mathbf{0}$.
 It is immediate that for all $\Lambda \subseteq \mathcal{L}$, the judgement

$$\text{subj}(\{\text{BC?m}\}) \vdash \text{B}^m \text{C}; \mathbf{0} : \langle \{\text{BC?m}\}, \Lambda \rangle$$

is not derivable because $\{\text{BC?m}\}$ is incomplete, in the sense that the label
 for the minimal event of B is not in $\{\text{BC?m}\}$. Nonetheless, $\{\text{BC?m}\}$ can be
 extended with labels $\phi \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ to obtain a derivable judgement. In this case, we
 take $\phi = \{\text{BC!m}\}$ and observe that

$$\text{subj}(\{\text{BC?m}\}) \cup \text{subj}(\phi) \vdash \text{B}^m \text{C}; \mathbf{0} : \langle \{\text{BC?m}\} \cup \phi, \Lambda \rangle$$

722 is derivable for $\Lambda = \{\text{BC!m}, \text{BC?m}\}$.

Lemma 37. *If $\Pi \triangleleft L$ and $\#\text{subj}(L \cap \mathcal{L}^!) \leq 1$ then there are $\phi, \Lambda \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ such that*
 724 *$\text{subj}(\phi) \subseteq \Pi$ and $\text{subj}(L) \cup \text{subj}(\phi) \vdash \langle L \rangle_\Pi : \langle L \cup \phi, \Lambda \rangle$.*

Proof. By induction on the derivation of $\Pi \triangleleft L$.

726 BASE CASE (\triangleleft -END). The thesis easily follows since $L = \emptyset$, hence $\langle L \rangle_\Pi = \mathbf{0}$ (by
 construction) and it suffices to take $\phi = \Lambda = \emptyset$ and apply rule (\triangleleft -T-END) to obtain
 728 the thesis.

CASE (\triangleleft -ACTIVE). If the derivation of $\Pi \triangleleft L$ ends with an instance of (\triangleleft -ACTIVE)
 730 then

$$L = \text{AB!m}, \text{AB?m}, L' \quad \Pi = \emptyset \quad \text{and} \quad A, B \triangleleft L'.$$

Therefore, by construction $\langle L \rangle_\Pi = \text{A}^m \text{B}; \langle L' \rangle_{A,B}$ and by inductive hypothesis
 732 we have that there exist $\phi_1, \Lambda_1 \in \mathcal{L}$ such that $\text{subj}(\phi_1) \subseteq \{A, B\}$ and $\text{subj}(L') \cup$

$\text{sbj}(\phi_1) \vdash \langle L' \rangle_{\{A, B\}} : \langle L' \cup \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle$. Then, we have the following typing:

$$\frac{\frac{\phi_{A, B} = \Lambda_{A, B} = \{A B!m, A B?m\}}{\{A, B\} \vdash A \xrightarrow{m} B : \langle \phi_{A, B}, \Lambda_{A, B} \rangle} \text{T-INT} \quad \frac{\vdots}{\text{sbj}(L') \cup \text{sbj}(\phi_1) \vdash \langle L' \rangle_{\{A, B\}} : \langle L' \cup \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle} \text{IH}}{\{A, B\} \cup \text{sbj}(L') \cup \text{sbj}(\phi) \vdash \langle L \rangle_{\Pi} : \langle \phi_{A, B} \cup ((L' \cup \phi_1) - \{A, B\}), \Lambda_1 \cup (\Lambda_{A, B} - (\text{sbj}(L') \cup \text{sbj}(\phi_1))) \rangle} \text{T-SEQ}$$

734 Take $\phi = \emptyset$ and $\Lambda = \Lambda_1 \cup (\Lambda_{A, B} - \text{sbj}(\phi_1))$, and note that

$$\begin{aligned} & \{A, B\} \cup \text{sbj}(L') \cup \text{sbj}(\phi) \\ &= \{A, B\} \cup \text{sbj}(L') && \text{because } \text{sbj}(\phi) = \emptyset \\ &= \text{sbj}(L) \cup \text{sbj}(\phi) && \text{because } \text{sbj}(\phi) = \emptyset \text{ and the definition of } L \\ \\ & \phi_{A, B} \cup ((L' \cup \phi_1) - \{A, B\}) \\ &= \phi_{A, B} \cup (L' - \{A, B\}) && \text{because } \text{sbj}(\phi_1) \subseteq \{A, B\} \\ &= \phi_{A, B} \cup L' && \text{because } A, B \triangleleft L' \text{ and Lemma 30 implies } A, B \notin \text{sbj}(L') \\ &= L \cup \phi && \text{because } \phi = \emptyset \text{ and of the definition of } \phi_{A, B} \\ \\ & \Lambda_1 \cup (\Lambda_{A, B} - (\text{sbj}(L') \cup \text{sbj}(\phi_1))) \\ &= \Lambda_1 \cup (\Lambda_{A, B} - \text{sbj}(\phi_1)) && \text{because } A, B \triangleleft L' \text{ and Lemma 30 implies } A, B \notin \text{sbj}(L') \\ &= \Lambda && \text{because of the definition of } \Lambda \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\text{sbj}(L) \cup \text{sbj}(\phi) \vdash \langle L \rangle_{\Pi} : \langle L \cup \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ holds.

736 CASE (\triangleleft -PASSIVE). If the derivation of $\Pi \triangleleft L$ ends with an instance of (\triangleleft -PASSIVE) then

$$L = A B?m, L' \quad \Pi = A, \Pi' \quad \text{and} \quad B, \Pi \triangleleft L'.$$

738 By construction $\langle L \rangle_{\Pi} = A \xrightarrow{m} B; \langle L' \rangle_{B, \Pi}$ with $A, B \notin \text{sbj}(L')$ (by Lemma 30) and
by inductive hypothesis there exist $\phi_1, \Lambda_1 \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ such that $\text{sbj}(\phi_1) \subseteq A, \Pi'$ and
740 $\text{sbj}(L') \cup \text{sbj}(\phi_1) \vdash \langle L' \rangle_{B, \Pi} : \langle L' \cup \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle$. Then, we have the following typing:

$$\frac{\frac{\phi_{A, B} = \Lambda_{A, B} = \{A B!m, A B?m\}}{\{A, B\} \vdash A \xrightarrow{m} B : \langle \phi_{A, B}, \Lambda_{A, B} \rangle} \text{T-INT} \quad \frac{\vdots}{\text{sbj}(L') \cup \text{sbj}(\phi_1) \vdash \langle L' \rangle_{\{A, B\}} : \langle L' \cup \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle} \text{IH}}{\{A, B\} \cup \text{sbj}(L') \cup \text{sbj}(\phi) \vdash \langle L \rangle_{\Pi} : \langle \phi_{A, B} \cup ((L' \cup \phi_1) - \{A, B\}), \Lambda_1 \cup (\Lambda_{A, B} - (\text{sbj}(L') \cup \text{sbj}(\phi_1))) \rangle} \text{T-SEQ}$$

742 The proof continues as in the previous case by taking $\phi = \emptyset$ and $\Lambda = \Lambda_1 \cup (\Lambda_{A, B} - \text{sbj}(\phi_1))$.

CASE (\triangleleft -COMP). We have $\sharp\Pi \neq 1$ and $L = L_1, L_2$ such that

$$\Pi \triangleleft L_1 \quad \Pi \triangleleft L_2 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{sbj}(L_1) = \text{sbj}(L_2) \neq \emptyset$$

744 with L , L_1 , and L_2 non-empty because of the last inequality. Hence, for $i \in \{1, 2\}$, there are $\phi_i, \Lambda_i \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ such that $\mathbf{sbj}(\phi_i) \subseteq \Pi$ and

$$\mathbf{sbj}(L_i) \cup \mathbf{sbj}(\phi_i) \vdash \langle L_i \rangle_{\Pi} : \langle L_i \cup \phi_i, \Lambda_i \rangle \quad (14)$$

746 CASE $\Pi = \emptyset$. By construction, $\langle L \rangle_{\Pi} = \langle L_1 \rangle_{\Pi} + \langle L_2 \rangle_{\Pi}$. By inductive hypothesis, there exist $\phi_i \subseteq \emptyset$ and Λ_i such that $\mathbf{sbj}(L_i) \cup \phi_i \vdash \langle L_i \rangle_{\Pi} : \langle L_i, \Lambda_i \rangle$ for $i = 1, 2$.
 748 Hence, $\phi_i = \emptyset$. It remains to check that $L_1 \bowtie_{\mathbf{sbj}(L_1)} L_2$. Since $\emptyset \triangleleft L_i$, $L_i \cap \mathcal{L}^! \neq \emptyset$ by Lemma 32. Moreover, $\#\mathbf{sbj}(L \cap \mathcal{L}^!) \leq 1$ by hypothesis. Hence, there is a
 750 unique $\mathbf{A} \in \Pi$ such that $\widehat{L}_i(\mathbf{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{L}^!$ and for all $\mathbf{B} \neq \mathbf{A} \in \Pi$, $\widehat{L}_i(\mathbf{B}) \subseteq \mathcal{L}^?$. Since L_1 and L_2 are disjoint, $\widehat{L}_1(\mathbf{A})$ and $\widehat{L}_2(\mathbf{A})$ are output uniform and $\widehat{L}_1(\mathbf{B})$ and
 752 $\widehat{L}_2(\mathbf{B})$ are input uniform. Moreover, $L_1 \cap L_2 = \emptyset$ ensures that $\widehat{L}_1(\mathbf{B}) = \emptyset$ if and only if $\widehat{L}_2(\mathbf{B}) = \emptyset$. Then, $L_1 \bowtie_{\emptyset} L_2$ holds.

754 The proof is completed by taking $\phi = \emptyset$ and $\Lambda = \Lambda_1 \cup \Lambda_2$ and noting that the following typing is derivable

$$\frac{\mathbf{sbj}(L_1) \vdash \langle L_1 \rangle : \langle L_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle \quad \mathbf{sbj}(L_2) \vdash \langle L_2 \rangle : \langle L_2, \Lambda_2 \rangle \quad L_1 \bowtie_{\mathbf{sbj}(L_1)} L_2}{\mathbf{sbj}(L_1) \vdash \langle L_1 \rangle + \langle L_2 \rangle : \langle L, \Lambda_1 \cup \Lambda_2 \rangle} \text{T-CH}$$

756 CASE $\#\Pi \geq 2$. By construction, $\langle L \rangle_{\Pi} = \mathbf{G}_1 + \mathbf{G}_2$ where, for a participant $\mathbf{A} \in \Pi$,

$$\mathbf{G}_1 = \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{\text{left}} \Pi; \langle L_1 \rangle_{\Pi} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{G}_2 = \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{\text{right}} \Pi; \langle L_2 \rangle_{\Pi}$$

758 We have $\phi_1 \bowtie_{\Pi} \phi_2$ by Proposition 35, Lemma 31, and Theorem 36. Therefore, we can apply rule (\triangleleft -T-CH) to the judgements (14) and obtain the thesis. \square

760 The following corollary is an immediate consequence of Theorem 36, Proposition 35, and Lemma 37.

762 **Corollary 38.** *Let $L \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ be a set of actions. If $\triangleleft L$ and $\mathbf{sbj}(L \cap \mathcal{L}^!) = \{\mathbf{A}\}$ for some $\mathbf{A} \in \mathcal{P}$ then*

- $\langle L \rangle$ is well-branched
- 764 • for all $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbf{sbj}(L)$, $\min(\llbracket \langle L \rangle \rrbracket \uparrow \mathbf{X}) = \widehat{L}(\mathbf{X})$
- there exists $\Lambda \in \mathcal{L}$ such that $\mathbf{sbj}(L) \vdash \langle L \rangle : \langle L, \Lambda \rangle$.

766 6.2. Well-formed sets of maximal events

768 As for minimal events, we identify the conditions that ensure that the typing context is inhabited by a ground g-choreography. Analogously, we introduce the *orderly concludes* relation that holds when the actions in L are the last actions
 770 of the participants in Π (dually to the relation \triangleleft).

Definition 39 (Orderly conclusions). *Let $\Pi \triangleright L$ be the smallest relation closed under the following rules:*

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\emptyset \triangleright \emptyset} \triangleright\text{-END} \qquad \frac{\Pi \triangleright L}{A, B, \Pi \triangleright AB!m, AB?m, L} \triangleright\text{-MATCHED} \\
\frac{B, \Pi \triangleright L}{A, B, \Pi \triangleright AB!m, L} \triangleright\text{-OUT} \qquad \frac{A, \Pi \triangleright L}{A, B, \Pi \triangleright AB?m, L} \triangleright\text{-IN} \\
\frac{\Pi \neq \emptyset \quad \Pi \triangleright L_1 \quad \Pi \triangleright L_2 \quad L_1 \neq L_2}{\Pi \triangleright L_1 \cup L_2} \triangleright\text{-COMP}
\end{array}$$

We now comment on the rules of Definition 39. Rule ($\triangleright\text{-END}$) states that no participant is responsible to orderly conclude an empty set of actions. Rule ($\triangleright\text{-MATCHED}$) allows us to add the sender and the receiver of two new actions provided that the remaining actions are orderly concluded by the other participants. Rule ($\triangleright\text{-OUT}$) (resp. ($\triangleright\text{-IN}$)) allows us to add the sender (resp. receiver) of an action provided that its receiver (resp. sender) can orderly conclude the remaining actions together with the other participants. Finally, rule ($\triangleright\text{-COMP}$) handles sets of actions corresponding to branches, namely sets of actions consisting of the non-trivial union of two sets L_1 and L_2 . In fact, the first and last condition respectively guarantee that both L_1 and L_2 are non-empty (cf. Lemma 41) and that they differ for at least one action; if this is the case the ($\triangleright\text{-COMP}$) requires that participants Π orderly execute the actions in both branches.

Example 40. *Let $L = \{BA?m, BC!n, CD!m, CD?m, DC!n, DC?n\}$. The derivation*

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{}{\emptyset \triangleright \emptyset} \triangleright\text{-END}}{\{C, D\} \triangleright \{CD!m, CD?m\}} \triangleright\text{-MATCHED} \quad \frac{\frac{}{\emptyset \triangleright \emptyset} \triangleright\text{-END}}{\{C, D\} \triangleright \{DC!n, DC?n\}} \triangleright\text{-MATCHED}}{\{C, D\} \triangleright \{CD!m, CD?m, DC!n, DC?n\}} \triangleright\text{-COMP}}{\{B, C, D\} \triangleright \{BC!n, CD!m, CD?m, DC!n, DC?n\}} \triangleright\text{-OUT}}{\{A, B, C, D\} \triangleright L} \triangleright\text{-IN}
\end{array}$$

establishes the judgement $\{A, B, C, D\} \triangleright L$. \diamond

Next results state properties of the orderly conclusions relation $\Pi \triangleright L$, which are instrumental for the proof of the main result in this section. The first one establishes that actions in L are associated with participants in Π .

Lemma 41. *If $\Pi \triangleright L$ then $\Pi = \text{sbj}(L)$.*

Proof. By straightforward induction on the derivation $\Pi \triangleright L$. \square

792 A set of actions L satisfying $\Pi \triangleright L$ corresponds to a well-typed g-choreography $\Pi \langle L \rangle$ whose maximal events are the actions in L , as formally defined below.

$$\Pi \langle L \rangle = \begin{cases} \mathbf{0} & \text{if } L = \emptyset \\ A \xrightarrow{m} B; \Pi' \langle L' \rangle & \text{if } L = AB!m, AB?m, L' \text{ and } \Pi = A, B, \Pi' \\ A \xrightarrow{m} B; A, \Pi' \langle L' \rangle & \text{if } L = AB?m, L' \text{ and } \Pi = A, B, \Pi' \\ A \xrightarrow{m} B; B, \Pi' \langle L' \rangle & \text{if } L = AB!m, L' \text{ and } \Pi = A, B, \Pi' \\ G + G' & \text{if } A \in \Pi \text{ and } L = L_1 \cup L_2 \text{ and } L_1 \neq L_2 \text{ and } \Pi \triangleright L_1 \text{ and} \\ & \Pi \triangleright L_2 \text{ and } G = A \xrightarrow{\text{left}} \Pi; \Pi \langle L_1 \rangle \text{ and } G' = A \xrightarrow{\text{right}} \Pi; \Pi \langle L_2 \rangle \end{cases}$$

794 **Example 42.** *consider the set of actions M in Example 40 and recall that $\{A, B, C, D\} \triangleright M$ holds. By applying the third case, we have that*

$$\{A, B, C, D\} \langle M \rangle = B \xrightarrow{m} A; \{B, C, D\} \langle BC!n, CD!m, CD?m, DC!n, DC?n \rangle$$

796 For $\{B, C, D\} \langle BC!n, CD!m, CD?m, DC!n, DC?n \rangle$, we apply the third case of the definition of $\langle _ \rangle$. Then,

$$\{B, C, D\} \langle BC!n, CD!m, CD?m, DC!n, DC?n \rangle = B \xrightarrow{n} C; \{C, D\} \langle CD!m, CD?m, DC!n, DC?n \rangle$$

798 Then, we apply the last case in the definition of $\langle _ \rangle$ by taking $L_1 = \{CD!m, CD?m\}$ and $L_2 = \{DC!n, DC?n\}$. Then,

$$\{C, D\} \langle CD!m, CD?m, DC!n, DC?n \rangle = C \xrightarrow{\text{left}} \{C, D\}; \{C, D\} \langle L_1 \rangle + C \xrightarrow{\text{right}} \{C, D\}; \{C, D\} \langle L_2 \rangle$$

Finally, by using the first and second rule, we can conclude that $\{C, D\} \langle L_1 \rangle = C \xrightarrow{m} D$ and $\{C, D\} \langle L_2 \rangle = D \xrightarrow{n} C$. \diamond

800 **Lemma 43.** *If $\Pi \triangleright L$ then $\Pi \langle L \rangle$ is defined.*

Proof. By straightforward induction on the derivation of the judgement $\Pi \triangleright L$. \square

Lemma 44. *If $\Pi \triangleright L$ then $\mathcal{P}(\Pi \langle L \rangle) = \Pi$.*

804 *Proof.* By straightforward induction on the derivation of the judgement $\Pi \triangleright L$. The only interesting case is $(\triangleright\text{-COMP})$, where the thesis follows because $\mathcal{P}(A \xrightarrow{_} \Pi; G) = \{A\} \cup \Pi \cup \mathcal{P}(G)$ holds for all A, Π and G . \square

Theorem 45. *If $\Pi \triangleright L$ then $\Pi \langle L \rangle$ is well-formed.*

808 *Proof.* By induction on the derivation of the judgement $\Pi \triangleright L$. Base case is immediate and all inductive cases but $(\triangleright\text{-COMP})$ follow by straightforward application of inductive hypothesis and the fact that the sequential composition of well-formed choreographies is well-formed. Case $(\triangleright\text{-COMP})$ is as follows. From 810 $\Pi \triangleright L_1$ and $\Pi \triangleright L_1$ we conclude that $\Pi \langle L_1 \rangle$ and $\Pi \langle L_1 \rangle$ are defined (by Lemma 43) and $\mathcal{P}(\Pi \langle L_1 \rangle)$ and $\mathcal{P}(\Pi \langle L_2 \rangle)$ (by Lemma 44). As in the proof of Theorem 36, 812

814 the definition of $_ \xrightarrow{\Pi}; _$ ensures that the resulting choice $G + G'$ is well-formed,
 namely

- 816 (i) there is a unique selector $A \in \Pi$,
- (ii) $\mathcal{P}(G) = \mathcal{P}(G')$, that is the sets of participants in both branches is the same,
- 818 and
- (iii) each $B \in \Pi \setminus \{A\}$ is passive and receives **left** on one branch and **right** on
 820 the other branch. \square

Lemma 46. *If $\Pi \triangleright L$ then there exists $\phi \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ such that $\text{sbj}(\phi) = \Pi$ and $\Pi \vdash$
 822 $\Pi(L) : \langle \phi, L \rangle$.*

Proof. By induction on the derivation of the judgement $\Pi \triangleright L$.

824 **BASE CASE (\triangleright -END).** Then, $L = \Pi = \emptyset$. Hence, $\Pi(L) = \mathbf{0}$ by construction. The
 thesis follows by taking $\phi = \emptyset$ and noting that $\emptyset \vdash \mathbf{0} : \langle \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$ follows by rule
 826 (\triangleright -END)

CASE (\triangleright -MATCHED). Then $L = \mathbf{AB!m, AB?m}, L'$ and $\Pi = \mathbf{A, B}, \Pi'$ and $\Pi' \triangleright L'$.
 828 Hence, $\Pi(L) = \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{m} \mathbf{B}; \Pi'(L')$. By inductive hypothesis, there exists $\phi' \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ such
 that $\text{sbj}(\phi') = \Pi'$ and $\Pi' \vdash \Pi'(L') : \langle \phi', L' \rangle$. Then, the following judgement is
 830 derivable

$$\frac{\frac{\phi'' = \Lambda'' = \{\mathbf{AB!m, AB?m}\}}{\{\mathbf{A, B}\} \vdash \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{m} \mathbf{B} : \langle \phi'', \Lambda'' \rangle} \text{T-INT} \quad \frac{\vdots}{\Pi' \vdash \Pi'(L') : \langle \phi', L' \rangle} \text{IH}}{\{\mathbf{A, B}\} \cup \Pi' \vdash \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{m} \mathbf{B}; \Pi'(L') : \langle \phi'' \cup (\phi' - \{\mathbf{A, B}\}), L' \cup (\Lambda'' - \Pi') \rangle} \text{T-SEQ}}$$

The proof is completed by taking $\phi = \phi'' \cup \phi'$ and by noting that $\{\mathbf{A, B}\} \cup \Pi' = \Pi$,
 832 $\phi'' \cup (\phi' - \{\mathbf{A, B}\}) = \phi'' \cup \phi' = \phi$ and $L' \cup (\Lambda'' - \Pi') = L' \cup \Lambda'' = L$, because
 $\text{sbj}(\phi') \cap \{\mathbf{A, B}\} = \emptyset$ and $\text{sbj}(\Lambda'') - \Pi' = \emptyset$.

834 **CASE (Λ -OUT).** Analogous to the previous one.

CASE (\triangleright -IN). Analogous to the previous one.

836 **CASE (\triangleright -COMP).** If the derivation of $\Pi \triangleleft L$ ends with an instance of (\triangleright -COMP) then

$$\frac{\Pi \neq \emptyset \quad \Pi \triangleright L_1 \quad \Pi \triangleright L_2 \quad L_1 \neq L_2}{\Pi \triangleright L_1 \cup L_2} \triangleright\text{-COMP}$$

By construction, $\Pi(L) = G_1 + G_2$ where, for an $A \in \Pi$,

$$G_1 = \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{\text{left}} \Pi; \Pi(L_1) \quad \text{and} \quad G_2 = \mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{\text{right}} \Pi; \Pi(L_2)$$

838 By inductive hypothesis, for $i \in \{1, 2\}$ there exist $\phi_i \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ such that $\text{sbj}(\phi_i) = \Pi_i$.
 By definition of $_ \xrightarrow{\Pi}; _$ we have $\Pi_i \vdash G_i : \langle \phi_i, L_i \rangle$. Moreover, $\phi_1 \bowtie_{\Pi} \phi_2$ since there
 840 is a unique selector A sending **left** on one branch and **right** on the other branch,

and each $B \in \Pi \setminus \{A\}$ is passive and receives **left** on one branch and **right** on the other. Hence, the following judgement is derivable:

$$\frac{\frac{\vdots}{\Pi_1 \vdash G_1 : \langle \phi'_1, L_1 \rangle} \text{IH}_1 \quad \frac{\vdots}{\Pi_2 \vdash G_2 : \langle \phi'_2, L_2 \rangle} \text{IH}_2 \quad \phi'_1 \bowtie_{\Pi} \phi'_2}{\Pi \vdash G_1 + G_2 : \langle \phi'_1 \cup \phi'_2, L_1 \cup L_2 \rangle} \text{T-CH}$$

The proof is completed by taking $\phi = \phi'_1 \cup \phi'_2$ and by noting that $L = L_1 \cup L_2$. \square

Theorem 47 (Inhabitation). *Let Π, ϕ, Λ be a typing context such that $\text{sbj}(\phi) = \text{sbj}(\Lambda) = \Pi$, $\text{sbj}(\phi \cap \mathcal{L}^!)$ is a singleton, $\triangleleft \phi$, and $\Pi \triangleright \Lambda$. Then, there exists a ground g -choreography G such that $\Pi \vdash G : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ is derivable.*

Proof. By Corollary 38, there exists $\Lambda' \in \mathcal{L}$ such that $\text{sbj}(\phi) = \Pi \vdash \langle \phi, \Lambda' \rangle$. By Lemma 46, there exists ϕ' such that $\text{sbj}(\phi') = \Pi$ and $\Pi \vdash_{\Pi} \langle \phi', \Lambda \rangle$. Then, $\Pi \vdash \langle \phi \rangle;_{\Pi} \langle \Lambda \rangle : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle$ holds by combining the judgements with (T-SEQ) as follows

$$\frac{\frac{\vdots}{\Pi \vdash \langle \phi \rangle : \langle \phi, \Lambda' \rangle} \text{COROLLARY 38} \quad \frac{\vdots}{\Pi \vdash_{\Pi} \langle \Lambda \rangle : \langle \phi', \Lambda \rangle} \text{LEMMA 46}}{\Pi \cup \Pi \vdash \langle \phi \rangle;_{\Pi} \langle \Lambda \rangle : \langle \phi \cup (\phi' - \Pi), \Lambda \cup (\Lambda' - \Pi) \rangle} \text{T-SEQ}$$

The proof is completed by taking $G = \langle \phi \rangle;_{\Pi} \langle \Lambda \rangle$ and noting that $\phi \cup (\phi' - \Pi) = \phi$ and $\Lambda \cup (\Lambda' - \Pi) = \Lambda$ because $\text{sbj}(\phi) = \Pi$ and $\text{sbj}(\Lambda) = \Pi$. \square

7. Typing rules for refinable choreographies

Combining the hypotheses in Theorem 26 and Theorem 47, we extend the typing system to refinable choreographies by the following typing rule:

$$\frac{\text{sbj}(\phi) = \text{sbj}(\Lambda) = \Pi \quad \text{sbj}(\phi \cap \mathcal{L}^!) = \{A\} \quad \triangleleft \phi \quad \Pi \triangleright \Lambda \quad \forall 1 \leq i \leq n : B_i \text{ eventually receives } m_i \text{ in } \Lambda}{\Pi \vdash A \xrightarrow{m_1 \dots m_n} B_1 \dots B_N : \langle \phi, \Lambda \rangle} \text{T-REF}$$

To illustrate what has been achieved by this extension of the typing system to refinable choreographies, let us resume example (2) from the Introduction:

$$C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S + C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S; S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C$$

Adapting from Example 20, and combining this derivation with a further premise
 860 to rule T-CH below, we have:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{}{\Pi \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{S} : \langle \phi_7, \Lambda_7 \rangle} \text{T-REF} \quad \frac{}{\Pi \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{req}} \mathbf{S} : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle} \text{T-REF} \quad \frac{}{\Pi \vdash \mathbf{S} \xrightarrow{\text{done}} \mathbf{C} : \langle \phi_2, \Lambda_2 \rangle} \text{T-REF} \\
 \frac{}{\Pi \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{req}} \mathbf{S}; \mathbf{S} \xrightarrow{\text{done}} \mathbf{C} : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_2 \rangle} \text{T-SEQ} \\
 \hline
 \frac{}{\Pi \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{S} + \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{req}} \mathbf{S}; \mathbf{S} \xrightarrow{\text{done}} \mathbf{C} : \langle \phi_7 \cup \phi_1, \Lambda_7 \cup \Lambda_2 \rangle} \text{T-CH}
 \end{array} \tag{15}$$

where $\Pi = \{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\}$, $\phi_7 = \Lambda_7 = \{\mathbf{CS}! \text{md}, \mathbf{CS}^? \text{md}\}$, $\phi_1 = \Lambda_1 = \{\mathbf{CS}! \text{req}, \mathbf{CS}^? \text{req}\}$
 862 and $\phi_2 = \Lambda_2 = \{\mathbf{SC}! \text{done}, \mathbf{SC}^? \text{done}\}$. By rule T-INT we derive:

$$\Pi \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{S} : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle, \quad \Pi \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{req}} \mathbf{S} : \langle \phi_2, \Lambda_2 \rangle, \quad \text{and} \quad \Pi \vdash \mathbf{S} \xrightarrow{\text{done}} \mathbf{C} : \langle \phi_3, \Lambda_3 \rangle.$$

Hence, by rule T-SEQ we have:

$$\frac{\frac{\phi_1 = \Lambda_1 = \{\mathbf{CS}! \text{req}, \mathbf{CS}^? \text{req}\}}{\{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\} \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{req}} \mathbf{S} : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle} \text{T-INT} \quad \frac{\phi_2 = \Lambda_2 = \{\mathbf{SC}! \text{done}, \mathbf{SC}^? \text{done}\}}{\{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\} \vdash \mathbf{S} \xrightarrow{\text{done}} \mathbf{C} : \langle \phi_2, \Lambda_2 \rangle} \text{T-INT}}{\{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}\} \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{req}} \mathbf{S}; \mathbf{S} \xrightarrow{\text{done}} \mathbf{C} : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_2 \rangle} \text{T-SEQ}$$

864 so that by T-CH we conclude that:

$$\Pi \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{S} + \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{req}} \mathbf{S}; \mathbf{S} \xrightarrow{\text{done}} \mathbf{C} : \langle \phi_7 \cup \phi_1, \Lambda_7 \cup \Lambda_2 \rangle$$

is derivable, and so that it refines (2) by Theorem 26.

Now, let's consider the g-choreography $\mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{B}; \mathbf{B} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{S}$, which can be checked
 to refine $\mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{S}$. But refining the latter with the former in the context

$$[\cdot] + \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{req}} \mathbf{S}; \mathbf{S} \xrightarrow{\text{done}} \mathbf{C}$$

866 spoils well-formedness. Indeed $\Pi \not\vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{B}; \mathbf{B} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{S} : \langle \phi_1, \Lambda_1 \rangle$. However, it suffices to take $\Pi' = \Pi \cup \{\mathbf{B}\} = \{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{S}, \mathbf{B}\}$ and $\Lambda_5 = \Lambda_1 \cup \{\mathbf{BS}! \text{md}\}$ to have that:

$$\frac{\frac{\phi_3 = \Lambda_3 = \{\mathbf{CB}! \text{md}, \mathbf{CB}^? \text{md}\}}{\{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{B}\} \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{B} : \langle \phi_3, \Lambda_3 \rangle} \text{T-INT} \quad \frac{\phi_4 = \Lambda_4 = \{\mathbf{BS}! \text{md}, \mathbf{BS}^? \text{md}\}}{\{\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{S}\} \vdash \mathbf{S} \xrightarrow{\text{done}} \mathbf{C} : \langle \phi_4, \Lambda_4 \rangle} \text{T-INT}}{\Pi' \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{B}; \mathbf{B} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{S} : \langle \phi_5, \Lambda_5 \rangle} \text{T-SEQ}$$

868 where

$$\begin{aligned}
 \phi_5 &= \phi_3 \cup (\phi_4 - \{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{B}\}) = \{\mathbf{CB}! \text{md}, \mathbf{CB}^? \text{md}, \mathbf{BS}^? \text{md}\} \\
 \Lambda_5 &= \Lambda_4 \cup (\Lambda_3 - \{\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{S}\}) = \{\mathbf{BS}! \text{md}, \mathbf{BS}^? \text{md}, \mathbf{CB}^? \text{md}\}
 \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand $\Pi' \vdash \mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{S} : \langle \phi_5, \Lambda_5 \rangle$ is an instance of T-REF. Incidentally
 870 we note that Π' , ϕ_5 , and Λ_5 are computable from $\mathbf{C} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{B}; \mathbf{B} \xrightarrow{\text{md}} \mathbf{S}$. Still we cannot

freely replace $\Pi' \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S : \langle \phi_5, \Lambda_5 \rangle$ in the derivation (15), because $\Pi' \neq \Pi$
 872 where the difference is B , making rule T-CH inapplicable.

However, by computing the typing context of $C \xrightarrow{x} B; B \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S$ we obtain

$$\Pi' \vdash C \xrightarrow{x} B; B \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S : \langle \phi_8, \Lambda_8 \rangle$$

874 where $\phi_8 = \{CB!x, CB?x, BS?req\}$ and $\Lambda_8 = \{CB!x, BS!req, BS?req\}$.

Now we can check that $\Pi' \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S : \langle \phi_8, \Lambda_8 \rangle$ is another instance of T-REF,
 876 so that $C \xrightarrow{x} B; B \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S \text{ ref } C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S$ by Theorem 26. Putting all together we have:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\Pi' \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S : \langle \phi_5, \Lambda_5 \rangle}{\text{T-REF}} \quad \frac{\frac{\Pi' \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S : \langle \phi_8, \Lambda_8 \rangle}{\text{T-REF}} \quad \frac{\Pi \vdash S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C : \langle \phi_2, \Lambda_2 \rangle}{\text{T-REF}}}{\Pi' \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S; S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C : \langle \phi_8, \Lambda_2 \rangle} \text{T-SEQ}}{\Pi' \vdash C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S + C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S; S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C : \langle \phi_5 \cup \phi_8, \Lambda_5 \cup \Lambda_2 \rangle} \text{T-CH}}$$

where $\phi_8 \cup (\phi_2 - \Pi') = \phi_8$ because $\text{subj}(\phi_2) = \Pi \subseteq \Pi'$ hence $\phi_2 - \Pi' = \emptyset$; similarly
 878 $\Lambda_2 \cup (\Lambda_8 - \Pi') = \Lambda_2$ since $\Lambda_8 - \Pi' = \emptyset$. From this derivation we conclude that
 we can safely replace $C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S$ with $C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} B; B \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S$, $C \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S$ with $C \xrightarrow{x} B; B \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S$
 880 and $S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C$ with $S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C$ obtaining

$$(C \xrightarrow{\text{md}} B; B \xrightarrow{\text{md}} S) + (C \xrightarrow{x} B; B \xrightarrow{\text{req}} S; S \xrightarrow{\text{done}} C)$$

which is a refinement of (2).

882 8. Conclusions & Related Work

We proposed a framework for refining the global views of choreographies.
 884 In the context of concurrent and distributed systems, refinement methods have
 received great attention in the 80-90's. Action refinement has been studied
 886 in different settings by adding refinement combinators to, e.g., process algebras
 [10], labelled event structures [11] and causal trees [12]. The cornerstone
 888 in this line of work is that actions, considered atomic at a given level of abstraction,
 are refined into processes or computations, which are non-atomic at a
 890 lower level of abstraction. For instance, a labelled event structure can be refined
 into another one by substituting all events that have a particular label by an
 event structure [11]. Analogously, a term of a process algebra can be refined
 892 into another one by replacing all occurrences of a particular action by a term.

A straightforward application of this approach to global choreographies would
 894 suggest to consider a standard language for choreographies, e.g., that one formalised
 in [7] and reproduced in Definition 5, and then to provide a substitution
 896 mechanism for its syntactical atomic constructs, which in this setting would be
 interactions $A \xrightarrow{m} B$. To improve expressibility of refinable interactions we opted
 898 for a generalised version $A \xrightarrow{m_1 \dots m_n} B_1 \dots B_N$ that allows for the explicit definition

900 of several participants involved in a complex, underspecified interaction. In this
way, we provide more flexibility for abstraction.

902 We might have considered a more general versions of refinable interactions,
e.g., by considering multiple senders on the left hand side of the arrow. We opted
904 for the current presentation because the standard well-formedness condition on
global choreographies introduces several limitations on the way in which such
906 abstractions could be implemented. E.g., they could not be refined as a choices
because of the standard constraint on the uniqueness of the active participant.
908 We plan to investigate suitable generalisations on the shape of refinable interac-
tions. For instance, multiple senders could be admitted in refinable interactions
910 provided that suitable constraints are put on the refining choreographies.

A semantics of g-choreographies in terms of pomsets [13] has been introduced
912 in [8, 7]. Pomsets can be envisaged as event structures with an empty conflict
relation. This semantics captures a more general notion of well-brancheness
914 than the one considered here. In principle, one could borrow this more gen-
eral notion of well-formedness in our framework at the cost of increasing the
916 technical execution. Despite that we associate global choreographies with event
structures (as previously done, e.g., in [14] to give semantics to multi-party
918 session types [15]), we remark that refinement techniques developed for event
structures cannot be straightforwardly lifted to the language of global chore-
920 ographies because the semantics of interactions is given in terms of two events.
Hence, the refinement of an interaction would translate into the refinement of
922 a sub-structure instead of a single event. This establishes an interesting con-
nection with previous work that we plan to investigate further. Along the same
924 lines, the main focus on previous work on refinement [10, 11, 12] is concerned
with the consistency of refinement with respect to the semantics of the language,
926 i.e., whether refinement preserves behavioural equivalences. Note that we have
left implicit the semantics of refinable interactions, which is given in terms of the
928 set of concrete realisations that it admits. An interesting line of work that we
envisage for future development is whether the proposed refinement preserves
930 equivalences.

The typing of ground g-choreography is unique (cf. Corollary 18). Actu-
932 ally, a simple inspection of the typing rules in Fig. 1 shows that type inference
is trivial for ground g-choreography. This is not the case for non-ground g-
934 choreographies where a type inference algorithm has to “guess” the types of
refinable actions. We leave type inference open and we will address it in the
936 future.

We also leave open the problem of which properties are maintained through
938 the refinement process, namely what can be established of abstract programs
that still holds of concrete ones. In particular, we would like to preserve well-
940 formedness of g-choreographies along refinements.

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